

D5.6

Synthesis and future strategy

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Deliverable abstract

ENVRI-FAIR is working towards the integration of (meta)data and service flows across the different environmental research infrastructures and to enhance the FAIRness of their (meta)data and services and enable efficient linking to EOSC. In this respect, FAIR Convergence of the participating research infrastructures will enable a tight integration of services and datasets from the participating ENVRI, to the benefit of various stakeholder categories. Convergence, both technological and conceptual, will support integration with the European Open Science Cloud. The current report D5.6 on *Synthesis and outlook* evaluates the current status of the FAIR convergence efforts done on the subdomain and cluster level and provides strategic recommendations for the future developments of the ENVRI and the ENVRI-Hub.

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DOCUMENT AMENDMENT PROCEDURE

Amendments, comments and suggestions should be sent to the Project Manager at manager@envri-fair.eu.

GLOSSARY

A relevant project glossary is included in Appendix A. The latest version of the master list of the glossary is available at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4471374>.

PROJECT SUMMARY

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and Biodiversity / Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity.

The overarching goal is that at the end of the proposed project, all participating RIs have built a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC.

This goal is reached by: (1) well defined community policies and standards on all steps of the data life cycle, aligned with the wider European policies, as well as with international developments; (2) each participating RI will have sustainable, transparent, and auditable data services, for each step of data life cycle, compliant to the FAIR principles. (3) the focus of the proposed work is put on the implementation of prototypes for testing pre-production services at each RI; the catalogue of prepared services is defined for each RI independently, depending on the maturity of the involved RIs; (4) the complete set of thematic data services and tools provided by the ENVRI cluster is exposed under the EOSC catalogue of services.

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D5.6 – Synthesis and future strategy

1 Introduction

One of the major goals of the ENVRI-FAIR project is to promote the adoption of the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016) in order to enhance the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of data within and across the Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI). Adoption of FAIR principles pertains to metadata, data, data streams and applications, all with the goal of increasing the exchange of FAIR data through converging standards and technology. **Convergence of the participating research infrastructures** (RIs) will enable a tight integration of services and datasets from the participating ENVRI, to the benefit of various stakeholder categories. Convergence, both technological and conceptual, will support emulation with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Convergence follows a two-pronged approach: through i) FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs, Schultes et al. 2020) and ii) a common catalogue of services¹ (Petzold et al., 2023).

To this aim, all ENVRI subdomains, through their affiliated RIs, provided meticulous assessment reports (Lund Myhre et al. 2023, Boulanger 2023, Vermeulen et al. 2023, Ferrighi 2023, Jeffery et al. 2020, Basset et al. 2023). The reports, supplemented by rigorously constructed, machine-actionable **FAIR Implementation Profiles** (FIPs) have been analysed both on subdomain and cluster level to assess quality and strength of the network established by shared **FERs** (a shared FER is a FER shared by two or more research RIs). Quality and strength of FER interlinkage were taken as a simple yet readily quantifiable proxy for RI convergence. In addition to the subdomain level assessments, updates on the evaluations of FAIR data services provided by selected RIs has been conducted in 2022 (Stocker et al. 2022).

1.1 FAIR convergence

Implementing the FAIR Principles requires numerous choices concerning the use of FAIR-Enabling Resources, be they commitments to domain-relevant standards or to infrastructure technologies. These collective decisions compose the FAIR Implementation Profile and are made on behalf of that community of practice. A **FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP, Schultes et al. 2020)** is a list of declared technology choices intended to implement each of the FAIR Guiding Principles, made as a collective decision by the members of a particular community of practice. FIPs are captured by means of a questionnaire that allows communities to collect FAIR implementation choices. The tool used for this approach is a customised instance of the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), named the FIP Wizard². The tool development was financed by CODATA (in 2020) and by the ENVRI-FAIR project (in 2021 and 2022). The FIP Wizard prompts a representative of the community (the Community Data Steward) to provide answers that explicitly profile the FAIR implementation approach of that community. FIPs are published by the FIP Wizard as FAIR (machine-readable) and Open data, which can then serve as a reference for practical FAIR data stewardship activities conducted by members throughout that community. FIP publication also encourages FIP reuse and repurposing by other communities, which saves time ‘reinventing the wheel’ and simultaneously drives convergence on FAIR implementation choices. Over time, FIPs need to be revised to reflect the evolving needs of the community and the ongoing development of FAIR technologies. The FIP Wizard supports versioning for a systematic revision, which in turn can provide insight into FAIR-related technology trends. A **FAIR Implementation Community (FIC)** is defined as a voluntary association of people and organisations that agree to adhere to the same FIP. The FAIR Implementation Community can be large or small, formal or informal, they can (but need not necessarily) be defined around a research infrastructure or a repository. The FIC is fundamentally important to FAIR and defining the FIC is the beginning of any FAIRification effort. A **FAIR Enabling Resource (FER)** is a digital object that provides functions needed to achieve some aspect of FAIRness addressing specific FAIR Sub-Principles. The FERs can be designated as either “available” for reuse or “in development”. For each of the FAIR principles there are defined types of FERs, see Table 1 below.

¹ see <https://envri-hub.envri.eu/>

² see <https://fip-wizard.ds-wizard.org/>

Table 1: Defined types for FAIR Enabling Resources

FAIR Sub-principle	Type of FAIR Enabling Resource	Definition
F1	identifier service	A service that provides for any digital object (1) algorithms guaranteeing global uniqueness, (2) policy document that guarantees persistent and (3) resolution of the identifier to machine-actionable metadata describing the object and its location.
F2	metadata schema	A specification that defines metadata fields describing attributes of data or other digital objects.
F3	metadata-Data linking schema	A specification that provides a unique, persistent, (ideally) bi-directional, machine-actionable link between metadata and the data they describe.
F4	registry	A service that indexes metadata and data and provides search over that index.
A1.1	communication protocol	A specification that defines how messages are structured and exchanged.
A1.2	authorization and authentication service	A service that mediates access to digital objects according to specified conditions.
A2	metadata preservation policy	A document that describes the conditions under which metadata are to be provisioned in the future (maybe part of a data management plan).
I1	knowledge representation language	A language specification whereby knowledge can be made processible by machines.
I2	structured vocabulary	A specification of uniquely identified and unambiguous concepts with their definitions represented preferably using web standards.
I3	semantic model	A specification that defines qualified relations between entities describing data or other digital objects using structured vocabularies.
R1.1	usage license	A document that describes the conditions under which a digital object can be legally used.
R1.2	provenance model	A specification that defines metadata fields describing the origin and lineage of data or other digital objects.
R1.3	FIP as a whole	

FIPs are not a goal in and of themselves. The primary purpose of creating and maintaining FIPs is to accelerate the wide-spread adoption of FAIR-enabling standards so that data and services will become increasingly interoperable and thus reduce the need for manual (human) intervention in routine data munging. Although it might have been previously viewed as luxury, given the large volumes and heterogeneous complexity of the scientific data, automated F, A, I, and R has by now become a necessity if the actual value inherent in data is to be realised.

Following the model of Wittenburg and Strawn (2018), the term *convergence* indicates a phase of infrastructure development when a critical mass of the stakeholder community chooses to deploy the same enabling technologies. Convergence by even a relatively small number of stakeholders often encourages the broader community to choose for the same approach, which may result in large-scale exploitation of the new infrastructure. In convergence, most stakeholders may not even be aware of the underlying standards and implementation technologies, but nonetheless use them and enjoy the benefits. In the emergence of the Internet, for example, TCP/IP was an "attractor" technology that precipitated the convergence among a limited number of influential early movers (mainly from private industry). Today, the vast majority of the users of the Internet are unaware of TCP/IP and many other technical aspects, having, knowingly or not, followed the lead of the early movers.

Convergence is one mechanism by which to accelerate the wide-spread adoption of FAIR-enabling Resources. However, in the case of FAIR, we aim for an Internet of Data and Services, hence, the "attractor" technology in this case will not be a single technology component like TCP/IP but a profile of technologies that includes the complex set of domain relevant standards (i.e., the FIP). For FAIR, convergence would then be seen as a critical mass of early movers who adopt the same or equivalent FIP. In FAIR convergence, we look for FIPs that act as "attractors" to a critical mass of early movers.

1.2 Validation and policies

ENVRI-FAIR also worked on the formulation of criteria and test plans for validating the overall quality of the ENVRI-FAIR data services and use cases towards the EOSC catalogue of services (Bailo et al. 2022), to which ENVRI-FAIR aims with the development of the ENVRI-Hub. In addition, Asmi et al. (2023) provided an outline on the transition from a theoretical policy framework, developed in a number of workshops, to the practical implementation of policy which needs to be considered. Key policy drivers, such as EOSC Rules of Participation, FAIR principles, and ENVRI-Hub initial documents have been analysed and incorporated into a draft framework. The document explores the distinctions between

Policies, Practices (Guidelines), and Technologies (IT Implementation) in Research Infrastructure management, emphasising interoperability and documentation and defining an ENVRI policy.

1.3 Task forces

In order to enhance knowledge sharing and consultancy on the development of common principles and knowledge sharing a number of Task Forces (TFs) has been set-up in ENVRI-FAIR. The TF have been formed along the FAIR principles dealing with

- F - Findability
 - TF1 ENVRI Catalogue of services
 - TF3 PIDs identification types and registries
- A - Accessibility
 - TF2 ENVRI (VO) AAI Implementation
- I - Interoperability
 - TF4 Triple stores and data storage certification
- R - Re-usability
 - TF5 Licences, citation, and usage tracking
- TF6 ENVRI-Hub design and architecture as transversal contribution to all FAIR Principles

TFs are instruments for consultancy, platforms for knowledge transfer and for identifying viable technology solutions, and thus supporting convergence on a cross-domain level and being the interface between the RI community and the supporting activities. TFs resulted in a number of conclusions which have been considered for the work beyond ENVRI-FAIR.

1.4 Aim of the document

The current work focused on the evaluation of the project efforts towards the enhancement of the FAIRness of, and across, the subdomains, and a synthesis of the overall progress of the ENVRI-FAIR services and their readiness for integration into the EOSC. This synthesis can be achieved by the overall FAIR convergence which is based on the FAIR assessments (FAs) conducted during the project lifetime to monitor the implementation efforts. This should result in a strategy for the future development of the ENVRI services. Based on the requirement analysis and technology review conducted by Magagna et al. (2020) in the first phase of the project, the current report aims to provide a synthesis and outlook of the efforts taken to enhance the FAIRness of the contributing RIs. These assessments and the FAIR convergence are the backbone of the work presented here.

Chapter 2 focuses on the methods applied and used in order to collect and analyse the FAIRness of the environmental research infrastructures (ENVRIs) participating in ENVRI-FAIR. Results and first discussions of the subdomain as well as on the cluster level are provided in Chapter 3. With ENVRI-FAIR major steps have been taken to enhance the FAIRness of the ENVRIs. Chapter 4 therefore provides an outlook on the next steps towards better integration and convergence. Summarising the work of ENVRI-FAIR based on the provided deliverables and analysis we try to make some strategic recommendations for the further development of the ENVRIs, the ENVRI-Hub and the integration into EOSC. This is summarised in Chapter 5 focusing the Strategy and outlook for FAIR RIs.

2 Methods

2.1 FAIR Assessment surveys

Within the scope of Task 5.1 and further extended in Task 5.5 of WP 5 ENVRI-FAIR was required to provide FAIR assessments on the “state-of-the-art” of the existing data and services of the involved research infrastructures. The starting point for the evaluation process was provided by maturity self-assessments prepared by the RI communities during the proposal preparation phase. The basic structure of the requirement collection and analysis can be summarised in the following steps:

1. Guided and systematic FAIRness self-assessment via the FAIR Implementation Profiles questionnaire Analysis of the gaps identified in each RI

2. Harmonisation in a common plan for each subdomain, to derive the first set of requirements to be integrated on RI level
3. Yearly updated FAIR Implementation Profiles
4. Newly identified requirements tracked during the project and eventually included in the common development actions (e.g., via the joint task forces, use cases and other development activities).

To effectively coordinate the FAIRness assessment (step 1) in all four subdomains and the overarching requirement analysis in WP5 and WP7, we focussed on:

1. Actively checking the latest progress from relevant initiatives, e.g., GO FAIR Foundation (GFF), RDA and EOSC,
2. Defining a FAIR assessment questionnaire together with the GFF Convergence Matrix team and provided customised templates for WP8-11 (i.e., the subdomain WPs) to perform their FAIRness assessment,
3. Actively contributing to the workshops organised by the subdomain WPs to support the FAIRness assessment process,
4. Reviewing the short-term development plans and prioritised actions proposed by each RI within their subdomain, harmonised the analysis within the subdomains and provided the cluster view on the FAIRness gaps and development plan.

Figure 1: The route to FAIR convergence

Over the lifetime of the project, four FAIR assessments (FAs) – one per year – were executed. The FA questionnaire structure evolved over time as it had to be developed and refined considering the experiences and feedback from the communities. To harmonise the results, the FA of the first run was re-interpreted and transferred into the structure of the updated FA questionnaire. In addition, the execution time of the FA was not at the same month of the year and in the last two runs it was done retrospectively for the year before. The FIP Wizard is essentially a questionnaire environment with 21 questions that ask the community representative to identify one or more FAIR Enabling Resources for each of the FAIR Principles, and with a separation of concern between metadata and data (with the exception of F2 and I2 that address only metadata and where F3 is requesting a resource that links metadata to data). R1.3 is not specifically requested as the whole FIP is interpreted as community specific metadata. Figure 1 and Table 2 gives an overview of the FA runs and the different approaches taken.

Table 2: FAIR assessment runs

run #	represented year	time of execution	FA method
1	2019	May-Jul 2019	google forms
2	2020	Oct-Nov 2020	FIP ver1
3	2021	Jan -Feb 2022	FIP ver2
4	2022	Jan - Mar 2023	FIP ver2

The first run of the FA in 2019 involved two questionnaires using Google Forms – the RDM questionnaire provided by GFF with 53 questions (see Magagna et al. 2020, Appendix 2) and the FAIR Maturity Indicators questionnaire with 25 questions based to assess the compliance with the FAIR principles. The first analysis immediately revealed that the responses to the questionnaires by the RI representatives were not directly usable for downstream analysis without substantial post-processing and harmonisation of the responses. The main problem of free text questionnaires is the one-to-many cardinality of certain questions when more than one answer is allowed. The follow up questions for example could relate to more than one resource described before, thus it becomes indistinct which resource is described further down. The survey was re-designed and merged the two questionnaires into one with 78 unambiguous questions in a new logical structure. In addition, the key information of the already provided answers was extracted and transformed into a structured form in YAML format, following a template also written in YAML. This result was reviewed and discussed in subdomain specific workshops supervised by FAIR experts. The YAML documents were converted into an RDF document (data.trig file) using a fully automated script implemented in Python as a Jupyter notebook that can be executed on EGI Notebooks service. The RDF documents were loaded into a triple store³ which allowed us to use SPARQL queries to fully exploit the information gathered.

After the first run a closer collaboration started with GFF which led to the establishment of the **Matrix Development Working Group**⁴. The goal was to co-develop a tool that makes it easy for communities to reuse existing solutions when implementing FAIR (choose to reuse) or to spot gaps and initialise new implementation developments where necessary (accepting a challenge to build something new). The Matrix should be a declaration / registration service to make it easy for communities to publicly announce their commitments to the reuse of existing, or to develop novel FAIR resources. Papers about FAIR resources and the matrix approach were published in 2020 (Jacobson et al, 2020; Sustkova et al, 2020).

These developments yielded two ontologies. One defines the FAIR vocabulary⁵ (by Tobias Kuhn) and the second advanced the matrix approach, conceptualising the FAIR Implementation Profile⁶.

A set of FERs using Wikidata⁷ references was gathered during the FIP events organised as Pre-Symposium Convergence Workshops⁸ (October/November 2020) with the involvement of 25 communities, where most of the ENVRI participants participated. This FA run#2 resulted in 20 ENVRI FIPs for the year 2020. For FA run#3 (ENVRI specific FIP Workshops)⁹ the FIP approach was revised (FIP ver2) using nanopublications instead of Wikidata references. All the FERs are represented and identified as RDF nanopublications which are fully expressed in a formal and machine-interpretable way. In addition, GFF started a process to qualify the resources according to the expert judgements and the GFF qualification criteria document¹⁰ which provides an own set of explicit interpretations and implementation considerations for each of the FAIR principles. GFF proposed definitions for all FER types which were evaluated by experts including ENVRI WP7 experts. The DSW-nanopub-API¹¹

³ <http://130.60.24.146:7883/sparql>

⁴ see <https://www.go-fair.org/today/fair-matrix/>

⁵ see <https://peta-pico.github.io/FAIR-nanopubs/principles/index-en.html>

⁶ see <https://peta-pico.github.io/FAIR-nanopubs/fip/index-en.html>

⁷ Wikidata is a collaboratively edited multilingual knowledge graph hosted by the Wikimedia Foundation

⁸ see <https://conference.codata.org/FAIRconvergence2020/sessions/258/>

⁹ see <https://envri.eu/event/fip-workshops-making-the-envris-fip-for-purpose-through-fair-convergence/>

¹⁰ see <https://osf.io/vzhda>

¹¹ see https://peta-pico.github.io/tapas/tapas.html?api=peta-pico/dsw-nanopub-api&op=/find_gofair_qualified_things

provides access to all GFF qualified resources. The FIP Wizard allows users to select a pre-curated list of FER nanopublications per question, which are garnished with a GFF badge if they were in fact qualified by GFF. A data steward can mint new FERs as nanopublications where needed within the FIP Wizard following specified templates, which are themselves expressed as small questionnaires that gather the essential metadata about a FER. This metadata corresponds to the assertion element of the nanopublication. A nanopublication¹² has in addition a provenance element, which describes how the assertion came to be and a publication info, which contains metadata about the nanopublication as a whole providing information about its creator and usage licence. In addition to FERs, FICs are also represented as nanopublications. The FIP as a whole is then composed of a set of assertions of the type: a <FIP-declaration> <declares current use of> a <resource>; <FIP-declaration> <declared by> a <community> and is expressed as a special kind of nanopublication called a nanopub index. In addition, it is possible to capture in the FIP Wizard information about the future use of a resource (is available or is in development) and the replacement of a resource with a new resource in future.

FER descriptions expressed as nanopublications need curation and quality-control. This is foreseen to be done by GFF-qualified facilitators. FER descriptions can be updated, enriched with mappings to other descriptions, and duplicated nanopublications retracted. GFF has started with a Fellowship¹³ and Training Programme¹⁴ to build up these work forces.

2.2 Evaluation of FAIR Implementation

Quantitative and qualitative analysis

The FIP information as reported by the participating research infrastructures via the FIP wizard (see above) was pulled from the DSW nanopub API¹⁵. Subsequently, a spreadsheet copy of the data was quality controlled with emphasis on the plausibility of implementation status and correct attribution to reporting periods. Of the numerous features available, the following were retained for analysis: 1. research infrastructure, 2. year, 3. FAIR principle, 4. FER, 5. implementation status.

Status and count of bilaterally shared FERs were used as proximity/activity measures for all further network assessments, the network nodes being RIs, FAIR principles or similar, depending on question and category (annual, subdomain etc.)

For most questions, grouping required some kind of aggregation of raw data. Status and count were summarised per group, depending on the question, in one of the following three ways:

1. To examine the strength of inter-RI connections, the lesser of each paired status was retained, assuming that this forms the bottleneck of bilateral exchange. To visualise: two RIs, A and B, both share a particular controlled vocabulary. However, this FER is fully implemented (status 3) at A while still in a test phase (status 1) at B. The implementation at B will thus throttle the bilateral exchange over this channel, regardless of the capacities at A.
2. General capacities (without focus on interaction between items) were assessed as the mean implementation status, weighted with FER count, per factor combination (e.g., per FAIR principle, year, and subdomain).
3. Similarity grouping used simple binary matrices (presence of a given FER) without any further weighting.

Based on these aggregates, data was visualised as heatmap, cluster dendrogram or network graph depending on the FIP quality to convey. In addition, information provided by specific FAIR assessment reports by the different subdomains (Lund Myhre et al. 2023, Boulanger 2023, Vermeulen et al. 2023, Ferrighi 2023, Jeffery et al. 2020, Basset et al. 2023) have been considered.

Network analysis

FER implementation status was classified as follows: (3) “fully implemented” defined as the FER is being fully implemented and used by the RI, (2) “planned use of developed resource” defined as the FER already being developed and planned to be used in the near future, (1) “planned use of resource to

¹² see https://nanopub.org/wordpress/?page_id=65

¹³ see <https://osf.io/x43g7>

¹⁴ see <https://osf.io/bthf8>

¹⁵ see https://peta-pico.github.io/tapas/tapas.html?api=peta-pico/dsw-nanopub-api&op=/make_matrix

be developed” defined as the FER is considered to be used but still needs to be developed or integrated, and (0) “no resource for this FAIR principle” defined as the FER is not considered to be used or implemented.

For the analysis the implementation status was averaged using mean values to calculate the “average implementation status”.

Network graphs were drawn using a force-directed layout. Such a layout considers the attracting/repelling forces between network nodes. The force two nodes attract each other with was considered the sum of edges (bilaterally shared FERs), each weighted with the edge’s strength (implementation status). As a result, the closer two nodes (RIs or repositories) are in the graph, the tighter they are interlinked by number and status of shared FERs (Figure 2).

Figure 2: An edge table (weighted connections between A and B) visualised as a force-directed network graph (Kamada-Kawai algorithm).

FIP similarities

The FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) describes inventory and implementation state of FAIR enabling resources (FERs) for a given unit, here: repository (Repo). To cluster repositories by FIP similarity, and v. v. FERs by their occurrence across repositories, we used the presence/ absence of a FER in a repository (regardless of within-repo frequency, e.g., same FER aiding multiple FAIR principles in the same repository).

Technically, this results in a matrix of zeros and ones spanning n repositories \times m FERs (across all repositories; Table 3). This initial matrix was used to calculate distances between repositories in an m -dimensional space. To visualise: the x- and y-coordinates of points A and B on a plane can be used to calculate their Euclidean distance as $(x^2 + y^2)^{0.5}$. Here, the x- and y-positions of repository A and B are determined by the absence (0) or presence (1) of two given FERs. As there were not only two but m FERs, distance was calculated for an m -dimensional space rather than a plane. Moreover, because FER presence is a discrete rather than a continuous quantity, the Manhattan rather than the Euclidean distance was used: where Euclidean distance measures the straight line between A and B, Manhattan distance counts the unit steps to get from A to B when only orthogonal moves are allowed (the name derives from the way one has to move around blocks of buildings).

The derived distance matrix (Manhattan metric) was used to cluster repository/FERs with the Ward¹⁶ method which maximises within-cluster homogeneity (Ward 1963). Figure 3 illustrates the principle for two dimensions (two FERs). Repositories were partitioned after inspection of the Ward-similarity based dendrograms: Such dendrograms illustrate the similarity between clusters by the height of the connecting bifurcation: the longer one has to travel along up and down branches from one (sub)cluster to the next, the lower the similarity. Branch length, when using the Ward method, is proportional to the increase in within-cluster variance (sum of squared distances from cluster centroid, normalised by cluster size) should the two clusters be merged.

Both for repositories and FERs, two clusters were regarded as the best trade-off between cluster homogeneity and specificity.

¹⁶ see overview of agglomerative cluster identification:
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hierarchical_clustering#Cluster_Linkage

Table 3: FER abundance matrix (patch) for clustering by FIP-similarity

	ORCID	DOI	Handle_System	UUID
	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>
ACTRIS-ARES	1	1	1	0
ACTRIS-ASC	0	1	0	1
ACTRIS_CLU	1	1	1	0
ACTRIS_DVAS	0	1	0	1
ACTRIS_GRES	1	1	0	1

Figure 3: Object (Repo) distances on a plane spanned by the vectors “FER 1 presence” and “FER 2” presence. A has neither FER implemented, B offers FER 1 only, D has both etc. A is closer to B and C, regarding its FER inventory than to D. Its Manhattan distance (in contrast to Euclidean distance, only discrete orthogonal moves are allowed) from B and C is 1, while it’s twice as far (two orthogonal unit moves required) from D.

2.3 Assessment of FAIR convergence

The analysis focused on the overlap and convergence of FERs used by the different RIs. As already outlined in the introduction, convergence can be defined as “... a phase of infrastructure development when a broad stakeholder community chooses to deploy the same enabling technologies ...”. This can be described by the use of shared FERs which are defined as “FER that is commonly used and implemented by at least two RIs and their repositories”.

Two convergence indicators were used to assess convergence: (a) the number of shared FERs as well as (b) the improvement of the implementation status of the FER.

We used the data from the FIP survey and identified the number of shared FERs either as absolute number of RIs and repositories or as relative share. In addition, the average implementation status was calculated based on the information provided in the FIP. This values ranged from (3) fully implemented, (2) planned use of developed resources, (1) planned use of resources to be developed, to (0) no resource for this FAIR principle. The implementation value (0) was annotated by the absence of information for a certain FER. Therefore, the values for the FIPs ranged from 1 to 3.

Additionally, when focusing on the FERs we also have to consider the importance of the FERs being shared between different RIs and repositories. Whereas for some the pure existence and use of a FER is important, e.g., PID for Findability (F), for others a common use of FERs or at least mappings between them is important, e.g., data schema for Interoperability (I). This we tried to address by using a qualitative description for the first case and the use of a quantitative indicator in the later. Table 4 summarises criteria and the indicators used to describe the convergence.

Table 4: Criteria/indicators describing the convergence between RIs and subdomains

Principle	Description of criteria	Indicator
F1	Global unique, and persistent identifiers (PID) need to be used to identify metadata as well as data. The persistence of the identifier is the most important aspect and depends on the reliability of the service provider.	qualitative description of PIDs used focusing on the shared FERs average implementation status
F2	The provision of rich and machine-readable metadata is an important prerequisite for the integration, discovery, and use of data. The use of common metadata schemas is important and should be a focus in the FAIR convergence. For this, crosswalks between the MD schemas are important and should be provided/developed.	number of shared FERs average implementation status
F3	This principle requires that the resource have metadata that is separated from the actual resource they describe but are persistently linked via identifiers bidirectional. In particular, it is expected that identifiers of digital objects behave in a predictable way so that the artificial agents can know what to expect when an identifier is resolved as it is defined in the FDOF specification ¹⁷ .	not addressed in the analysis, as currently there are not many implementations covering these requirements
F4	Providing common endpoints for users to discover and access metadata and data is important. An important aspect is the quality of the registries in terms of information covered and ingested from the providing MD sources. The use of shared indexing registries (e.g., GEOSS) is important and a common use of them within a given domain is important.	number of shared FERs average implementation status
A1.1	The use of common and open protocols for the exchange of metadata and data to enable cross system implementation	number of shared FERs average implementation status
A1.2	The use of interoperable authorisation and authentication systems is important to establish cross-RI services. An overlap of authentication and authorisation procedures is therefore beneficial.	number of shared FERs average implementation status
A2	Metadata longevity is important but was not addressed in the FIPs for most of the repositories. Here the sole existence of solutions and mechanisms is important.	not addressed in the analysis
I1	This principle focuses on the use of formal, shared and broadly applicable languages for knowledge representation. A common shared use of data formats and schemas is beneficial, and mappings are needed to ensure interoperability.	number of shared FERs average implementation status
I2	The use of common and shared vocabularies following FAIR principles should be fostered and is beneficial. In addition, mappings between	number of shared FERs average implementation status

¹⁷ <https://fairdigitalobjectframework.org/>

Principle	Description of criteria	Indicator
	vocabularies are needed to ensure interoperability.	
I3	(Meta)data include qualified reference to other (meta)data. This is focusing on conceptual models using linked data (called semantic models in the FIP Ontology ¹⁸). A common approach is needed, and overlaps are advantageous	number of shared FERs average implementation status
R1.1	This principle focuses on providing a clear and accessible data usage licence enabling the re-usability. Machine-readability is beneficial to ensure re-usability.	qualitative description of data usage licences average implementation status
R1.2	The description of provenance in the data life cycle is an important part of the re-usability and acknowledgement. Overlap of models to describe provenance is beneficial. Otherwise, mappings between provenance models are needed.	number of shared FERs average implementation status

Data are represented on the level of the subdomains showing the convergence between the RIs of a subdomain and on the cluster level to describe the overall trend.

3 Results

The results are based on the FAIR assessment conducted in the frame of the ENVRI-FAIR project. For the periods 2019, 2020, 2021, and 2022 FIPs for 15 RIs describing 22 repositories have been documented. In total, 85 FIPs were provided by the 15 RIs covering 22 repositories within the ENVRI-FAIR project period monitoring the progress of enhancing the FAIRness of the different RIs (see Table 5). EPOS-ERIC and Danubius did not contribute to the FIP round 2019, as well as AnaEE_CREA did not provide a FIP in 2023. The results of the first FAIR Assessment round in 2019, which was done in a slightly different method, were transformed, and migrated to the current version of the FIP wizard in order to enable the analysis of the FAIR convergence over the project period. It is important to state that EPOS-ERIC provided FIPs for 8 repositories in 2019 and from 2020 onwards only on the level of the RI. Therefore, the information from 2019 was aggregated to a summarised FIP in order to comply with the structure. This data has been used for the current analysis.

It is important to mention that in the following analysis ICOS and SIOS are accounted for each of the subdomains and are included in the analysis.

For the analysis, we are focusing on the cluster and subdomain level, without going into detail on specific information on the participating RIs. This information is provided by specific FAIR assessment reports by the different subdomains (Lund Myhre et al. 2023, Boulanger 2023, Vermeulen et al. 2023, Ferrighi 2023, Jeffery et al. 2020, Basset et al. 2023).

3.1 FAIR implementation and convergence

3.1.1 Overview

In total 206 Fair Enabling Resources (**FERs**) have been documented addressing the four FAIR principles covering all four years of the FAIR Assessment survey (see Annex A). Table 5 provides an overview on the total number of unique FERs for the different years of the evaluation. As ICOS and SIOS are assigned to more than one subdomain but providing only one FIP per year, the information was counted in each

¹⁸ <https://w3id.org/fair/fip/terms/Semantic-model>

of the subdomains. The number of unique FERs used by the different RIs ranged from 4 to 43 in the period covered. The list of unique FERs is provided in the annex.

On average we see a slight raise or same numbers of FERs for each of the RIs and documented repositories over time. These numbers should be seen as reference for the further analysis provided in the following analysis.

Table 5: Number of unique FERs documented for the different survey years per RI. Note that ICOS and SIOS are placed in more than one subdomain but provided only one FIP per survey year.

Domain	RI	Repository	2019	2020	2021	2022
ATM	ACTRIS	ACTRIS_CLU	12	12	16	17
		ACTRIS_DVAS	4	4	14	17
		ACTRIS_GRES	20	21	26	27
		ACTRIS_InSitu	8	15	19	21
		ACTRIS-ARES	7	7	20	25
		ACTRIS-ASC	16	16	21	21
	EISCAT 3D	EISCAT	14	16	18	15
	IAGOS	iagos	28	30	32	36
ICOS	ICOS	30	43	43	43	
SIOS	sios	21	24	23	29	
MAR	ArgoGdac	ArgoGdac	17	16	20	25
	EMSO	EMSO	15	15	12	12
	ICOS	ICOS	30	43	43	43
	LifeWatch-ERIC	lw-marine	24	29	29	32
	SeaDataNet	SeaDataNet-CDI	22	29	33	36
		SeaDataNet-Sextant	17	17	20	20
SOL	EPOS-ERIC	EPOS-ERIC	22		15	27
ECO	Anaee	Anaee	17	19	20	20
		AnaEE_CREA	12	12	12	
	DANUBIUS	DANUBIUS	7		16	16
	DiSSCo	DiSSCo	9	19	20	18
	eLTER-RI	eLTER-RI	28	29	30	36
	ICOS	ICOS	30	43	43	43
	LifeWatch-ERIC	LWERIC_Ecosystem	22	34	36	33
	SIOS	sios	21	24	23	29

Table 5 shows the number of unique FERs on subdomain level for the different FAIR principles in the different years. This ranged from 3 to 49 with a big variety between the solid earth subdomain and the other subdomains. The atmosphere, marine and ecosystem & biodiversity subdomain show the same range of unique FERs running between 26 and 47 for Findability (F), 16 and 33 for Accessibility (A), 22 and 49 for Interoperability (I), and 6 to 14 for Re-Usability (R).

Table 6: Number of unique FERs per subdomain split by FAIR principles.

FIP	Domain	F	A	I	R
2019	ATM	27	19	23	7
	MAR	30	16	27	13
	SOL	4	7	8	2
	ECO	26	21	39	6
2020	ATM	35	25	22	7
	MAR	31	23	26	14
	SOL				
	ECO	42	29	46	7
2021	ATM	35	26	26	9
	MAR	40	27	30	13
	SOL	3	7	5	2
	ECO	46	31	49	8
2022	ATM	39	28	29	11
	MAR	39	28	33	13
	SOL	5	9	10	2
	ECO	47	33	49	8
	<i>min</i>	3	7	5	2
	<i>max</i>	47	33	49	14

Table 7: Number of unique FERs on cluster level split by the FAIR principles.

FIP	F	A	I	R
2019	55	36	65	18
2020	59	39	65	19
2021	74	42	75	20
2022	79	46	80	17
<i>min</i>	55	36	65	17
<i>max</i>	79	46	80	20

Focusing on the cluster level the total number of documented unique FERs increased over the period covered (see Table 6), showing that additional FERs were selected and used by the different RIs. This could be due to better documentation of the FIPs in the later phases of the survey. Nevertheless, the number of unique FERs is slightly increasing in the last two years of the survey, which can be interpreted as an effect of the development of the FAIRness of the RIs. Table 7 shows the number of unique FERs for the surveyed RIs summarised on cluster levels considering all FIPs provided.

Details on the most common FERs are given in the detailed analysis on the FAIR principles on cluster and subdomain level. The documented and used FERs range from 17 to 80 with a more frequent use of FERs for Findability (F) and Interoperability (I).

3.1.2 Convergence and shared FERs on subdomain level

Indicators for assessing the convergence between the RIs are the *number of shared FERs* and the *improvement of the implementation status* over time. In total 79 unique FERs (out of the 203 documented FERs) are shared and commonly used at least by two RIs and their repositories. The number of shared unique FERs increased from 50 in 2019 to 71 in 2022. This shows a more common use of FERs within the project time of ENVRI-FAIR and is also a result of the implementation efforts taken in the project (see e.g., Lund Myhre et al., 2023).

Across research institutions (RIs) the FAIR implementation profile grew in variety (count of different FERs) and quality (implementation status). Particularly the principles Interoperability and Reusability improved over the four years (Figure 4).

Figure 4: The FAIR implementation profiles became richer (larger FER variety) and better (higher implementation status) over the course of the project.

To analyse the convergence, heatmaps for the shared FERs have been developed taking into account (a) the number of shared FERs between the RIs and (b) the average implementation status of the shared FERs. As for EPOS-ERIC only one FIP for the year 2022 has been documented, we do not provide a heatmap and detailed analysis for this RI. The data on EPOS are included in the cluster level analysis.

Subdomain “atmosphere”

Number and Implementation status of shared FERs increase for all FAIR principles from 2019 to 2022 (Figure 5). The atmospheric subdomain in ENVRI-FAIR consists of five RIs (ACTRIS, EISCAT, IAGOS ICOS and SIOS) which provided FIPs for ten repositories. Figure 5 represents the number of shared FERs weighted by the average implementation status between the RIs (including the repositories) of the subdomain “atmosphere” across the FAIR principles and the survey years. The highest similarity is between ACTRIS, IAGOS, ICOS, SIOS also showing an increasing number of shared FERs and implementation status in time. EISCAT-3D shows the lowest number of shared FERs with the other RIs in the subdomain. This is also true for 2022.

Figure 5: Implementation status of the FAIR principles for the atmosphere Subdomain. F, A, I, and R increased from 2019 to 2022. The figure shows the annual count (symbol size) and average status of FERs shared among “atmosphere” RIs.

This pattern is present when focusing on all FAIR principles, except for Re-Usability (R) where it only can be shown in 2022, which is due to the implementation efforts taken in the frame of the ENVRI-FAIR project (Lund Myhre et al. 2023). For the FAIR principle Re-Usability (R) a greater convergence towards commonly used FERs in 2022 can be shown between ACTRIS, EISCAT-3D, IAGOS and ICOS (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Heatmap of shared FERs for the subdomain “atmosphere” showing the number of shared FERs (number) and the FER count weighted by the average implementation status (saturation) coded by colour saturation.

The network analysis (see Figure 7) shows a stronger convergence of IAGOS, ACTRIS, ICOS, and SIOS from 2019 to 2020 which is expressed by the spatial distance in the network graph. RIs being nearer to each other show a higher similarity than being distanced from each other. The network graph also shows the shared FERs between the RIs highlighted by the labels and the size identifying the number and average implementation status. The shared FERs for all FAIR principles are included in the network graph. Details on the shared FERs is given in the following analysis.

2019

2022

Figure 7: Network graphs of shared FERs in the subdomain “atmosphere” across all FAIR principles: upper panel indicates 2019 and lower panel indicates 2022. The shared FERs are highlighted as labels and the size of the shared FERs reflects the frequency and implementation status and the distance between the RIs reflects their similarity in the FIP.

Overall, the percentage of shared FERs (ratio of number of shared FERs related to the total number of FERs given in percent) increased for all FAIR principles from 2019 to 2022 (see Table 8).

For **Findability (F)** principle F1, dealing with the use of globally unique and persistent identifiers, DOIs (50%), Handle PIDs (30%), and UUIDs (30%) have been the most common shared FERs in 2019 which

extended in 2022 to DOIs (90%), Handle PID (50%), ePIC (30%), and UUID (40%). This shows an increase in commonly used PID systems across the RIs. In addition, in 2022 the use of PIDs for other information types, like ORCID for persons (30%) and ROR for organisations (20%) was mentioned. For the sub-principle F2, focusing on the description with rich metadata and the use of commonly used metadata schemas, the number of shared FERs increased from 2 to 3 in the period surveyed with a stronger focus on the use of the WMO Core Profile in 2022 (50%), which was adopted as common standard by the subdomain in the project runtime and thus enhancing the convergence and interoperability. For the sub-principle F4, focusing on the indexing and sharing of metadata in a common searchable resource, the number of catalogues indexing the metadata increased from 1 to 4. In 2019 DataCite (30%) and EUDAT B2FIND (20%) was mentioned which was extended to GEOSS Portal, WMO Search, and r3data in 2022 enhancing the findability of the data sources.

The use of shared FERs for **Accessibility (A)** increased from 2019 to 2022 whereas the unique FER number stayed stable which shows a convergence in use. The most common shared FERs in 2019 as well as in 2022 for the sub-principle A1.1, focusing on standardised protocols for data and metadata retrieval, are HTTP/HTTPS (2019 and 2022 100%), OpenDAP (2019 60%, 2022 80%), REST (2019 60%, 2022 70%) and FTP (2019 20%, 2022 20%). OpenDAP and REST showed an increase in use by the different repositories in the subdomain and its implementation status. For the sub-principle A1.2, focussing on the authorisation and authentication procedures, within the subdomain eduGAIN (20%) and OAuth (20%) were the most shared FERs in 2019 and was extended in use by other repositories in the subdomain in 2022 (eduGAIN n=3, OAuth n=3, SAML1.1 n=2). In addition, 7 of the 10 repositories mentioned OpenData both in 2019 and 2022 as the main procedure for data access.

The use of shared FERs for **Interoperability (I)** increased between 2019 and 2022 meaning that more repositories were implementing FERs of the same type and that the implementation status improved over the project time. In total the number of the unique shared FERs did not change. For the sub-principle I1, focusing on the language for knowledge and data representation, NetCDF (2019 70%, 2022 90%), as well as XML (2019 and 2022 40%), json (2019 30%, 2022 50%) are the most prominent ones mentioned in the FIPs. For the sub-principle I2, focusing on the use of FAIR vocabularies, GCMD is the one commonly used vocabulary across some repositories (40%). Nevertheless, a wide range of specific vocabularies are used by the different RIs which shows the importance of FAIR vocabularies and mappings between them where appropriate. For I3, dealing with the (meta)data schemata used, NetCDF CF (2019 70%, 2022 80%) and NETCDF CF format SeaDataNet Profile (2022 60%) showed a slight increase in use for data. For metadata ISO19115 (2019 and 2022 40%) and WMO Core Profile (2019 20%, 2022 40%) are the most prominent ones.

For the **Re-Usability (R)** the use of clear licences as well as the use of a common language to document data provenance increased in the project time. For the sub-principle R1.1, focusing on data usage licence, 9 of the 10 repositories in the subdomain applied the CC-BY licence in 2022 while in 2019 it only had been 4. Also, the use of PROV-O, linked to sub-principle R1.2, increased during the project period with only 30% repositories in 2019 and 80% repositories in 2022.

Table 8: Percentage of repositories having the same shared FER for the subdomain ‘atmosphere’ (values in % of the documented repositories (FIP, total number of repositories = 10))

Principle	FER	2019	2020	2021	2022
F	F1 DOI	50%	70%	90%	90%
	F1 Handle_System	30%	20%	40%	50%
	F1 UUID	30%	30%	40%	40%
	F1 ePIC	0%	30%	30%	30%
	F1 sios_site	0%	0%	20%	20%
	F1 ORCID	0%	0%	30%	30%
	F1 ROR	0%	0%	0%	20%
	F2 wmo-core-profile	0%	40%	40%	50%
	F2 datacite_metadata_scheme	50%	50%	60%	50%
	F2 ISO_19115/19139	50%	40%	40%	40%
	F4 DataCite	30%	40%	60%	60%
	F4 WMO_Search	0%	20%	40%	40%
	F4 GEOSS_Portal	0%	30%	30%	40%
	F4 B2FIND	20%	20%	20%	20%
	F4 r3data	0%	0%	20%	20%
A	A1.1 HTTPS/HTTP	100%	100%	100%	100%
	A1.1 OPeNDAP	60%	70%	80%	80%
	A1.1 REST	60%	60%	60%	70%
	A1.1 OPENDATA	70%	70%	70%	70%
	A1.1 FTP	20%	20%	20%	20%
	A1.1 OGC WCS	0%	20%	20%	20%
	A1.1 OGC WMS	0%	20%	20%	20%
	A1.1 SPARQL_endpoint	0%	0%	20%	0%
	A1.1 OAI-PMH	40%	50%	60%	50%
	A1.1 OGC CSW	30%	40%	40%	40%
	A1.2 eduGAIN	20%	30%	30%	30%
	A1.2 OAuth	20%	20%	30%	30%
A1.2 SAML1.1	0%	0%	20%	0%	
I	I1 NetCDF	70%	80%	90%	90%
	I1 JSON	30%	30%	40%	50%
	I1 XML_Schema	40%	40%	40%	40%
	I1 RDFS	20%	20%	20%	20%
	I2 GCMD	40%	40%	40%	40%
	I3 NetCDF_CF1.7	70%	80%	80%	80%
	I3 CF_SN	30%	30%	50%	60%
	I3 wmo-core-profile	20%	30%	30%	40%
	I3 ISO_19115	40%	40%	40%	40%
	I3 datacite_metadata_scheme	0%	0%	20%	30%
R	R1.1 CC-BY-4.0	40%	40%	80%	90%
	R1.1 CC0-1.0	0%	20%	20%	40%
	R1.2 PROV-O	30%	30%	80%	80%

There has been strong progress and evolution of FAIRness within the atmospheric subdomain well documented in this report and Lund Myhre et al, 2023 with convergence to common solutions over the project period. Joint achievements across the subdomain opens new opportunities and synergies, and in particular the following joint achievements can be mentioned

- Gap analysis of FAIR-ness and the resulting one shared implementation plan to guide and coordinate across the subdomain the development in other related projects as well
- Common reference vocabulary for observed variables in atmospheric subdomain
- Common concept for identifying entities in data production
- Common concept for identifying entities in data production
- Agreement on common base technology for authentication

- Common concept for attribution, citation string and acknowledgement
- Common concept for licences on data products across RI.
- Metadata mapping to DCAT-AP and services registered in ENVRI-Hub
- Implementation of common protocols on machine-to-machine level to provide access to (meta)data

Subdomain “marine”

The subdomain “marine” consists of 5 RIs (SeaDataNet, LifeWatch_marine, ARGO, EMSO and ICOS) and 6 repositories (2 for SeaDataNet and 1 for the other RIs) being assessed with respect to their data and metadata FAIRness using a FIP questionnaire in the framework of the ENVRI-FAIR project.

For all FAIR principles, the number of shared FERs has increased from 2019 to 2022, and so did the overall implementation status (except for F where the already high level of 2019 was kept despite a 36% increase in FER count): Figure 8.

Figure 9 shows the heatmaps about the use of common and shared FERs between the RIs in the marine subdomain.

Which RIs share the greatest overlaps depends on the FAIR principle and the FIP year. For the year 2022 and for Findability (F), ARGO and ICOS on one hand and LifeWatch and ICOS on the other hand shared the highest number of FERs (13). For Accessibility (A), ICOS and SeaDataNet really stand out with 20 shared FERs. For Interoperability (I), ARGO and SeaDataNet shared the greatest number of FERs (18). Finally, for Reusability (R), the overlap is more homogenous between RIs, with LifeWatch and ICOS sharing a (slightly) greatest number of FERs (7).

Figure 8: Implementation status of the FAIR principles for the marine Subdomain. F, A, I, and R increased from 2019 to 2022. The figure shows the annual count (symbol size) and average status of FERs shared among “marine” RIs.

There is an overall greater convergence throughout the years (covered by the FIP survey) with increasing number of shared FERs and implementation status.

Figure 9: Heatmap of shared FERs for the subdomain "marine" showing the number of shared FERs weighted by the average implementation status (saturation) [figure: heatmap_marine.png]

The network analysis (see Figure 10) shows a stronger convergence of EMSO, ARGO and SeaDataNet from 2019 to 2022, which is represented by the spatial distance in the graph: RIs being nearer to each other show a higher similarity. The figure also labels the shared FERs - their number and average implementation status are highlighted by the font size.

2019

2022

Figure 10: Network graph of shared FERs in the subdomain “marine” across all FAIR principles: upper panel indicates 2019 and lower panel indicates 2022. The shared FERs are high-lighted as labels and the size of the shared FERs reflects the frequency and implementation status and the distance between the RIs reflects their similarity in the FIP.

Overall, the number of shared FERs for most of the FAIR principles remained rather stable for the period from 2019 to 2022 (see Table 9) but for some the common use increased.

For the sub-principle F1 of **Findability (F)**, dealing with the use of persistent unique identifiers, DOI (83%) was the most prominent PID used by the majority of the RIs and repositories. This remained stable over the years. For F2, dealing with data and metadata schema, ISO19115/19139 (50%) and schema.org (2022 50%) were the most prominent ones. This is also due to the fact that geo-spatial data play an important role in the marine domain. Despite the fact that a number of domain specific data portals and metadata platforms are implemented, Google Data Search (67%) was used as a common data search platform and thus widening the user community.

The number of shared FERs for **Accessibility (A)** increased between 2019 and 2022. For A1.1, dealing with the use of standardised protocols, HTTP/HTTPS (2022 83%), ERDAP (2022 67%) and SPARQL (50%) are the most prominent ones. For A1.2, dealing with the authentication and authorisation procedures, OpenData as a common procedure was the most prominent ones (67%). In addition, a number of AAI protocols are used by the RIs but not commonly shared. This also did not change in the runtime of the ENVRI-FAIR project.

Focusing on the **Interoperability (I)** the number of shared FERs stayed stable but the common use by the repositories increased in the period surveyed. RDFS (2019 67%, 2022 83%), NetCDF (2019 50%, 2022 67%) and XML Schema (50%) were the most prominent FERs for the sub-principle I1, dealing with the schemata for knowledge representation. For I2, dealing with FAIR vocabularies, NERC Vocabulary Server (2019 67%, 2022 83%) is the most commonly used vocabularies. In addition a number of RI specific vocabularies has been documented. For data the most commonly used schemata (sub-principle I3) is NetCDF CF1.7 (2019 33%, 2022 67%). For metadata schema.org (2022 33%) and DataCite Metadata Schema (33%).

For **Re-Usability (R)** the number of shared FERs stayed stable and the use slightly increased in the surveyed period. CC-BY-4.0 (2019 83%, 2022 100%) was the most widely used data usage licence (R1.1). To document the provenance PROV-O was considered and used by two thirds of the repositories, enabling machine-readable sharing of provenance information. The use of PROV-O did not increase in the surveyed period.

Table 9: Percentage of repositories having the same shared FER for the subdomain ‘marine’ (values in % of the documented repositories (FIP, total number of repositories = 6))

Principles	FER	2019	2020	2021	2022
F	F1 DOI	83%	83%	83%	83%
	F1 URI	33%	33%	33%	33%
	F1 Handle_System	33%	33%	33%	33%
	F1 ePIC	33%	33%	33%	33%
	F2 datacite_metadata_scheme	33%	33%	33%	33%
	F2 ISO_19115	50%	33%	50%	50%
	F2 Schema.org_Dataset	33%	33%	50%	50%
	F2 DCAT-AP	0%	33%	33%	33%
	F4 Google_Dataset_Search	33%	67%	67%	67%
	F4 DataCite	33%	33%	33%	33%
	F4 Google	0%	33%	33%	33%
	F4 B2FIND	0%	0%	33%	33%
A	A1.1 HTTPS/HTTP	50%	67%	83%	83%
	A1.1 OPENDATA	83%	67%	67%	67%
	A1.1 ERDDAP	33%	67%	67%	67%
	A1.1 REST	33%	33%	33%	33%
	A1.1 SPARQL_endpoint	0%	33%	50%	50%
	A1.1 OGC WMS	0%	33%	33%	33%
	A1.1 OAI-PMH	33%	50%	50%	50%
	A1.1 OGC CSW	0%	33%	33%	33%
I	I1 RDFS	67%	67%	83%	83%
	I1 NetCDF	50%	50%	67%	67%
	I1 XML_Schema	50%	50%	50%	50%
	I1 JSON-LD	0%	33%	33%	33%
	I1 OWL	0%	0%	0%	33%
	I1 DwC-A	33%	0%	0%	0%
	I2 NVS_Voc	67%	83%	83%	83%
	I2 WoRMS	0%	0%	0%	33%
	I3 NetCDF_CF1.7	33%	50%	50%	67%
	I3 Schema.org_Dataset	0%	0%	33%	33%
	I3 datacite_metadata_scheme	33%	33%	33%	33%
I3 DCAT-AP	0%	0%	0%	33%	
R	R1.1 CC-BY-4.0	83%	83%	100%	100%
	R1.1 CC0-1.0	50%	50%	33%	33%
	R1.2 PROV-O	67%	50%	67%	67%

Within the project framework efforts have been taken to enhance the convergence of the participating RIs. In particular, this encompassed the use of the NERC Vocabulary Server (NVS)¹⁹ by Argo and the development of the data broker (EOV broker) with the associated SPARQL and ERDDAP technologies by marine RIs. It is noteworthy that it may not be relevant to reach a greater convergence for every FER. For instance, in most marine RIs, there is no authentication required to access the data. This means that to increase the convergence for a FER related to authentication would not be relevant in this case.

As mentioned in the conclusion of Alviset et al. (2022), the ENVRI-FAIR project was a driving force into the improvement of this FAIRness. The FAIRness coverage has greatly increased. At the time, the deliverable D9.9 (Alviset et al., 2022) was written, there were still some needed FERs to complete the FAIRness for a very few FIP questions/RI (regarding longevity plan, persistent identifiers linking data to metadata and licensing). Since then, LifeWatch has completed 2 out of the 3 unanswered FIP questions with operational FERs and the last one should be soon covered as a FER is under development.

¹⁹ see <https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/>

There is a need to develop/define a strategy to sustain the services, and to adapt them to evolving user needs. In this objective, 10 recommendations regarding data and metadata sustainability were detailed in Dobler et al. (2023): they covered a wide range of aspects including financial, technical and environmental aspects. In particular, we can cite here the recommendation n°3 about assessing the quality of the implementation of FERs and not only the FER usage status, the recommendation n°4 about basic set of common vocabularies, the recommendation n°5 about data volume increase, the recommendation n°6 about open-source code sharing, and finally, the recommendation n°8 about traceability. These recommendations from the marine subdomain are recalled and detailed hereinafter in the Strategy and outlook section.

Subdomain “solid earth”

The subdomain ‘solid earth’ contains one RI (EPOS) which operates a number of repositories. For 2019 a total of 8 repositories had been documented but for the years 2021 and 2022 only one FIP was provided. We assume that this includes the main shared FERs between the repositories. The data from 2019 had been aggregated to one FIP for 2019, to be compliant in the analysis. Table 10 provides an overview on the shared resources for the EPOS-ERIC split by the different FAIR principles.

The overall FAIR status of solid-earth repos already started off with the highest rating in 2019 for accessibility, interoperability and reproducibility, and this high level could be maintained for A and R, while I experienced a slight drop, whereas F improved by an equal amount from 2019 to 2022 (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Implementation status of the FAIR principles for the solid-earth Subdomain. F, A, I, and R increased from 2019 to 2022. The figure shows the annual count (symbol size) and average status of FERs shared among “solid-earth” RIs.

Table 10: List of shared FER for the subdomain ‘solid-earth’ (‘x’ indicates the mention in the FIP survey round))

Principles	FER	2019	2021	2022
F	DOI			x
	F1 ORCID		x	
	URI	x		x
	F2 EPOS-DCAT-AP	x	x	x
	EPOS-Metadata-Model	x		x
	F3 DOI			x
	EPOS-DCAT-AP	x		x
	F4 EPOS_Portal	x	x	x
A	HTTP	x		x
	HTTPS	x	x	x
	A1.1 REST		x	x
	WFS	x	x	x
	WMS	x	x	x
	eduGAIN			x
	EGI_checkin		x	
	A1.2 OAuth	x	x	x
	OPENDATA		x	
	OpenID	x		x
A2 epos-data-policy	x		x	
I	jpeg	x		x
	JSON	x		x
	JSON_Schema		x	
	I1 pdf			x
	png	x		x
	RDF	x		x
	tiff	x		x
	XML_Schema		x	
	CERIF	x		x
	I2 DCAT2	x		x
	EPOS_vocab		x	x
	CERIF		x	
	I3 DCAT-AP	x		x
EPOS-DCAT-AP		x		
R	R1.1 CC-BY-4.0	x	x	x
	CC-BY-NC-4.0	x		x
	R1.2 CERIF		x	

Within the project framework efforts have been taken to achieve further convergence within the solid earth subdomain by focusing on the detailed implementation of the FAIR principles within EPOS (European Plate Observing System) and EMSO (European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory). EPOS contributed to the Force11 FAIR principles and so, naturally, EPOS was designed from the beginning to be FAIR.

In its endeavour of integrating various research infrastructures and data sets, from geology to seismology, to facilitate an integrated approach to solid earth sciences in Europe, EPOS worked on several fronts to improve the FAIR convergence:

- Gap Analysis: To continuously improve, EPOS conducts gap analysis to identify areas where improvements can be made in terms of FAIR principles.
- Metadata Enrichment and Standardization: EPOS focused on enriching and standardising metadata across its services. The metadata for different services, such as seismology, geodesy, volcanology, etc., is harmonised to ensure consistency and reusability.
- Integration with EMSO: For improved utilisation of marine data, EPOS collaborated with EMSO. The objective was to increase interoperability of geophysical data and metadata of

EMSO and EPOS by adopting common standards. This is particularly focused on data and sensors of Ocean Bottom Seismometers, Hydrophones, and Magnetometers, which are portable modules used in marine areas. Enriched metadata is expected to improve data documentation and ensure its re-use.

- d) Technical Activities and Implementation: EPOS was also involved in technical activities to ensure the adoption of FAIR principles. This includes analysis of available EMSO sources of seismic-related data, implementation of a harmonisation abstraction layer, quality control support on seismological data, and development of an appropriate FAIRness assessment process.
- e) Integration with ORFEUS-EIDA: EPOS has a workflow that includes interactions with ORFEUS-EIDA for seismic data. The focus is on ensuring better integration with ORFEUS-EIDA and harmonising access interfaces across EMSO regional facilities. This is crucial for ensuring that data is findable and accessible.
- f) Services and Data Catalogue: EPOS created a rich data catalogue with metadata. This catalogue is integrated with services and is made available to researchers and the broader community. The catalogue also incorporates data from the thematic communities within the EPOS RI, to ensure broader data availability.
- g) Glossary and Terminologies: EPOS also focused on developing a glossary and terminologies to ensure that the data and services are easily understandable and usable.

Subdomain “ecosystem & biodiversity”

Throughout the FAIR principles, the 2019 implementation status could be maintained by 2022, despite considerable increases in the number of FERs adopted for F, A and I (Figure 12).

The subdomain “ecosystem and biodiversity” consists of 7 RIs and 8 repositories being described with a FIP in the frame of the ENVRI-FAIR project. Figure 13 shows the heatmap and use of the common and shared FERs between the RIs and repositories in the subdomain. Given the high diversity in the ecosystem and biodiversity subdomain the highest overlaps meaning number of shared FERs can be shown between AnaEE, SIOS and Danubius as one group as well as between LifeWatch, eLTER and ICOS as the other.

Figure 12: Implementation status of the FAIR principles for the biodiversity and ecosystem Subdomain. F, A, I, and R increased from 2019 to 2022. The figure shows the annual count (symbol size) and average status of FERs shared among “biodiversity and ecosystem” RIs.

Overall, a greater convergence between the years covered by the FIP survey with increasing number of shared FERs and implementation status can be shown.

Figure 13: Heatmap of shared FERs for the subdomain “ecosystem & biodiversity” showing the number of shared FERs and the number of FERs weighted by the average implementation status (saturation) [figure: heatmap_ecosystem.png]

The network analysis (see Figure 14) shows a stronger convergence of AnaEE, SIOS and Danubius from 2019 to 2020 which is expressed by the spatial distance in the graph. RIs being nearer to each other show a higher similarity than being distanced from each other. For the subdomain marine in total six repositories have been described by a FIP. The figure also includes the shared FERs focusing on all FAIR principles which are highlighted by the labels and the size identifying the number and average implementation status.

2019

2022

Figure 14: Network graph of shared FERs in the subdomain “ecosystem and biodiversity” across all FAIR principles: upper panel indicates 2019 and lower panel indicates 2022. The shared FERs are high-lighted as labels and the size of the shared FERs reflects the frequency and implementation status and the distance between the RIs reflects their similarity in the FIP

Overall, the number of shared FERs for most of the FAIR principles increased slightly for the period from 2019 to 2022 (see Table 11) across the RIs of the subdomain ecosystem and biodiversity.

For **Findability (F)** DOI (75%) and Handle systems (50%) are the most commonly used FERs for the persistent identification of (meta)data (sub-principle F1). In addition a number of PIDs are implemented and used by the different RIs, enabling the persistent identification. Referring to sub-principle F2, dealing

with the metadata schemata used, ISO19115/19139 (50%) was the most commonly used metadata schemata. In addition, within the site documentation use case a mapping of site metadata to DCAT was developed. It appears that there is no clear convergence towards a single implementation choice, which might be due to the data challenges addressed by the different RIs (ref D11.6). A range of catalogues have been implemented by the different RIs sharing metadata by machine-readable interfaces (e.g., OGC CSW, OAI-PMH, REST, SPARQL). But DataCite (38%) and EUDAT B2FIND (25%) are the most common central metadata indexing platforms.

Focusing on **Accessibility (A)** for sub-principle A1.1, dealing with the use of standardised protocols, HTTP/HTTPS (75%) as well as OGC CSW (50%) for metadata are the most commonly used. OPENDATA (50%) and eduGAIN (25%) are the most widely used AAI protocols and procedures (A1.2). In addition, local identity providers for authorisation and authentication are used.

For **Interoperability (I)** as common language for knowledge representation (I1) XML Schema (63%) and NetCDF (63%) are the most prominent ones. In addition, DwC Archive (25%) is mentioned for biodiversity observation data. Due to the complexity and heterogeneity of the ecosystem and biodiversity domain, a number of vocabularies are used. Therefore, no common vocabulary could be identified (sub-principle I2). Enabling the semantic linking and mapping, e.g., by the use of the I-ADOPT (RDA Working Group on Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology²⁰) recommendations (Magagna et al., 2022) and ontology is an important step for the future development. Focusing the schemas used for (meta)data (sub-principle I3) NetCDF CF1.7 (38%) for data and ISO19115/19139 (38%) for metadata were the most common ones.

The provision of a clear data usage licence is the main aspect of the sub-principle R1.1 in **Re-Usability (R)**. Here the use of CC licences for data and metadata were the most commonly used FERs. CC-BY-4.0 was adopted by 75% of the repositories aiming for an open sharing of data by ensuring a clear reference and citation of the data use. The use of PROV-O as means to document provenance in a machine-readable manner (R1.2) is implemented or being implemented in the near future by 50% of the repositories.

²⁰ see <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/interoperable-descriptions-observable-property-terminology-wg-i-adopt-wg>

Table 11: Percentage of repositories having the same shared FER for the subdomain ‘biodiversity and ecosystem’ (values in % of the documented repositories (FIP, total number of repositories = 8))

Principles	FER	2019	2020	2021	2022
F	F1 DOI	88%	75%	88%	75%
	F1 Handle_System	38%	25%	38%	50%
	F1 UUID	25%	25%	25%	38%
	F2 ISO_19115/19139	50%	38%	50%	50%
	F2 Schema.org_Dataset	0%	25%	25%	0%
	F2 DCAT-AP	0%	25%	25%	25%
	F2 DCAT2	0%	0%	0%	25%
	F4 DataCite	25%	25%	25%	38%
	F4 B2FIND	25%	25%	25%	25%
	F4 WMO_Search	0%	0%	0%	25%
	F4 GeoNetwork	0%	0%	25%	25%
A	A1.1 HTTPS/HTTP	75%	75%	75%	63%
	A1.1 OPeNDAP	25%	25%	38%	38%
	A1.1 REST	25%	38%	38%	38%
	A1.1 OGC WMS	25%	38%	38%	38%
	A1.1 OGC CSW	38%	50%	50%	50%
	A1.1 OAI-PMH	38%	38%	38%	38%
	A1.2 OPENDATA	50%	50%	50%	50%
	A1.2 eduGAIN	0%	0%	25%	25%
	A1.2 LDAP	25%	25%	25%	0%
	A1.2 SAML2	0%	0%	25%	0%
	A1.2 ERDDAP	0%	25%	0%	0%
A1.2 OAuth	25%	25%	25%	0%	
I	I1 XML_Schema	63%	63%	63%	63%
	I1 NetCDF	63%	50%	63%	63%
	I1 DwC-A	25%	25%	25%	25%
	I1 RDFS	38%	25%	38%	25%
	I1 JSON-LD	0%	0%	25%	25%
	I1 JSON_Schema	0%	25%	25%	25%
	I2 EnvThes	0%	25%	0%	0%
	I3 NetCDF_CF1.7	25%	25%	38%	38%
	I3 ISO_19115	38%	38%	38%	38%
	I3 ISO_19139	25%	25%	25%	25%
	I2 NVS_Voc	0%	0%	25%	25%
	I3 wmo-core-profile	0%	0%	0%	25%
	I3 CF_SN	0%	25%	25%	25%
I3 DCAT2	0%	25%	25%	0%	
I3 DCAT-AP	0%	0%	25%	0%	
R	R1.1 CC-BY-4.0	88%	75%	88%	75%
	R1.1 CC0-1.0	50%	50%	50%	50%
	R1.1 CC-BY-NC-4.0	25%	25%	25%	38%
	R1.2 PROV-O	63%	63%	63%	50%

Overall, it can be said that clear steps have been taken in the Biodiversity and Ecosystem domain in general and in the RIs in particular in making data FAIR but further steps are necessary.

The main issue is related to the fact that the domain is highly heterogeneous and interdisciplinary. Indeed, within the Biodiversity and Ecosystem domain, RIs range from those dealing with museum specimens

(such as DiSScO), those primarily focused on monitoring (such as eLTER, ICOS), to those more oriented towards biodiversity observation (such as LifeWatch).

Within the project framework, efforts have been taken to enhance the convergence of the participating RIs. This encompassed the choice to make more interoperable the RIs having higher FAIRness and maturity levels and to identify and share the best practices to follow for the RIs with minor FAIRness and maturity levels, by establishing a sort of technological baseline in order to facilitate the network required for the implementation of FAIR principles in the RIs of WP11 and the broader ENVRI cluster. However, the future implementation and sustainability of these efforts will depend on the availability of budgets from new projects and the governance choices made by the individual RIs. Continued support and funding will be crucial in ensuring the long-term success and impact of the FAIR initiatives across the European research landscape. It is imperative that stakeholders continue to prioritise the adoption of FAIR principles to enable greater accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data, ultimately fostering scientific advancements and collaboration in the environmental domain.

3.1.3 Convergence and shared FERs on cluster level

As already indicated for the different subdomains, also the pattern of more common shared FERs and a raise in the implementation status can be seen on the cluster level. Across all RIs and years, the FAIR principles **F**(indability) and **A**(ccessibility) are currently implemented furthest. While **R**(eusability) still lags the other FAIR principles it experienced the strongest improvement since the first evaluation (Figure 15)

Figure 15: The implementation status of the FAIR principles F, A, I, and R increased from 2019 to 2022. Reusability grew strongest.

In order to assess and focus on the convergence across the subdomains we had a look at the shared “shared FERs” across the different subdomains. This means, that each FER was taken into account which was shared at least between two repositories within the subdomain and was shared between at least two subdomains. Plotting the heatmap of the shared FERs on the cluster level (see Figure 16) we can show, that by and large, FER-mediated coherence among subdomains increased continuously from 2019 to 2022, judging from the relative weight of shared FER-bundles (count × average implementation status of all FERs of identical FAIR-purpose and year), with the highest coherence attained between ecosystem and atmosphere infrastructures.

Figure 16: The number and implementation status of shared FERs increased steadily from 2019 to 2022. (Numbers: count of shared FERs where 100 = maximum across years and subdomains; saturation increasing with importance [implementation status × count])

This means that the number of shared FERs between the subdomains as well as the implementation status increased over time. We also analysed the unique FERs which were shared by at least two subdomains. This is based on the data summarised for the shared FERs by the subdomains. The results are shown in Table 12 which shows the common shared FERs across the subdomains. The sum indicates the number of subdomains using the same shared FER. Based on the data shown in the table we can see (as also in the heatmap) a wider common use of shared FERs even across the different subdomains resulting in a higher convergence. For many of the shared unique FERs the subdomains atmosphere, marine, and biodiversity and ecosystems showed a higher similarity than with solid earth.

Within the FAIR principle **Findability (F)** focusing on the global and persistent identification of (meta)data (F1) DOI and Handle System are the most common across the subdomains. The use of DOI was also adopted by EPOS-ERIC in 2022. In addition, ePIC Handle, URI and UUID are used by at least two of the subdomains. ISO19115/19139 as a generic MD schema for mainly geo-spatial data is the most commonly used schemata (sub-principle F2) except for EPOS. In addition, DCAT and DataCite MD Schema are used by at least two of the subdomains. As metadata search engines, where metadata of the different repositories are indexed (sub-principle F4) DataCite, B2FIND as well as WMO Search were the most common ones in 2022. As already analysed on the subdomain level a wide number of search engines and metadata portals are provided and serviced by the repositories.

When dealing with **Accessibility (A)** focusing on the use of standardised protocols for (meta)data retrieval by ID (sub-principle A1.1) HTTP/HTTPS (MD/Data), REST (MD/Data), OGC CSW (MD), OAI-PMH (MD), and OGC WMS (Data) were the most common in 2022. In addition, a variety of different services and protocols are used for the exchange of (meta)data, depending on the specific needs

and user community requirements. Focusing on the authorisation and authentication (A1.2) eduGAIN, OPENDATA (no need for authentication and authorisation), as well as OAuth were the most commonly used FERs in 2022. Here the use of a common AAI procedure would be good to enable cross-domain accessibility.

For **Interoperability (I)** focusing on the use of a formal, accessible, shared and broadly used language for knowledge representation (sub-principle I1) XML Schema, RDFS, as well as NetCDF are the most commonly used. In addition, json and json-LD play an important role for 3 of the subdomains. Focusing on the use of FAIR vocabularies (sub-principle I2) the Nerc Vocabulary Service (NVS) is the most common one shared by the marine and the biodiversity and ecosystem subdomain. As already shown for the different subdomains a wide range of vocabularies are used. This raises the need for mapping between the FAIR semantic resources and addressing interoperability issues. For the qualified reference to other (meta)data (sub-principle I3) NetCDF CF1.7, WMO Core Profile, ISO19115/19139, DataCite MD Schema, DCAT and schema.org MD Schema are at least used by two subdomain in 2022. Here overlap and common use of the schemata across the subdomains would be beneficial and mappings between the different models should be developed.

When focusing on Re-usability (R) the use of an accessible and clear data usage licence (subprinciple R1.1) is important. Across all subdomains CC-BY-4.0 (data) as well as CC0-1.0 (MD) are the most commonly used data usage licence. For R1.2, dealing with the association of provenance with the (meta)data, PROV-O (at least on a testing level) is used by most of the subdomains.

Table 12: Identification of shared FERs on cluster level indicating which FERs are shared at least by 2 subdomains split by the FAIR principles (data: based on the shared FERs per subdomain) and sorted by the number of subdomains sharing a FER in 2022. The shading indicates the number of subdomains sharing a FER: dark grey 3-4 subdomains, grey 2 subdomains, light grey 1 subdomain.

FAIR	FER	2019					2022					
		ATM	ECO	MAR	SOL	Sum	ATM	ECO	MAR	SOL	Sum	
F1	DOI	1	1	1		3	1	1	1	1	4	
	Handle_System	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3	
	ePIC			1		1	1		1		2	
	URI			1	1	2			1	1	2	
	UUID	1	1			2	1	1			2	
	ROR						1				1	
	sios_site						1				1	
	ORCID						1				1	
	F2	ISO_19115/19139	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3
		DCAT-AP							1	1		2
		datacite_metadata_scheme	1		1		2	1		1		2
		Schema.org_Dataset			1		1			1		1
		DCAT2							1			1
		wmo-core-profile						1				1
		EPOS-Metadata-Model				1	1				1	1
EPOS-DCAT-AP					1	1				1	1	
F4		DataCite	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3
		B2FIND	1	1			2	1	1	1		3
	WMO_Search						1	1			2	
	Google_Dataset_Search			1		1			1		1	
	Google								1		1	
	r3data						1				1	
	EPOS_Portal				1	1				1	1	
	GeoNetwork							1			1	
	GEOSS_Portal						1				1	
	A1.1	REST	1	1	1		3	1	1	1	1	4
HTTPS/HTTP		1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	4	
OGC CSW		1	1			2	1	1	1		3	
OAI-PMH		1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3	
OGC WMS				1		1	1	1	1		3	
OPeNDAP		1	1			2	1	1			2	
SPARQL_endpoint									1		1	
WMS					1	1				1	1	
WFS					1	1				1	1	
OGC WCS							1				1	
ERDDAP				1		1			1		1	
FTP		1				1	1				1	
A1.2		eduGAIN	1				1	1	1		1	3
		OPeNDATA	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3
		OAuth	1	1		1	3	1	?		1	2
	OpenID				1	1				1	1	
	LDAP			1		1					1	
	I1	XML_Schema	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3
		RDFS	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3
NetCDF		1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3	
JSON		1			1	2	1			1	2	
JSON-LD								1	1		2	
JSON_Schema								1			1	
png					1	1				1	1	
RDF					1	1				1	1	
jpeg					1	1				1	1	
tiff					1	1				1	1	
DwC-A			1	1		2		1	?		1	
pdf										1	1	
OWL										1	1	
I2		NVS_Voc		?	1		1		1	1		2
		WoRMS								1		1
	GCMD	1				1	1				1	
	DCAT2				1	1				1	1	
	CERIF				1	1				1	1	
	EPOS_vocab									1	1	
	EnvThes		?					?				
B	NetCDF_CF1.7	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3	
	wmo-core-profile	1				1	1	1			2	
	ISO_19115	1	1			2	1	1			2	
	CF_SN	1				1	1	1			2	
	datacite_metadata_scheme			1		1	1		1		2	
	DCAT-AP				1	1			1	1	2	
	Schema.org_Dataset								1		1	
	ISO_19139			1		1		1			1	
	R1.1	CC-BY-4.0	1	1	1	1	4	1	1	1	1	4
		CC0-1.0		1	1		2	1	1	1		3
CC-BY-NC-4.0			1		1	2		1		1	2	
R1.2		PROV-O	1	1	1		3	1	1	1		3
		CERIF				1	1				1	1
		27	26	24	19	96	39	34	34	24	131	

Analysing the network cohesion is taken as a measure for the FAIR convergence. This considers the number and identity of shared FERs as well as the implementation status for the FERs documented by

the different RIs calculating the vertex connectivity (see Chapter 2.2 on Network analysis). An indicator for the FAIR convergence is the average overall implementation status of the shared FERs. Both shared FER count and status can be taken to describe if shared FERs are used by the different RIs and thus increase the level of interoperability and reusability of data and data streams.

Figure 17 illustrates the multitude of FERs tightly connecting research infrastructures by 2022 and also gives an impression of the considerable amount of FERs reaching out to other infrastructures.

atmosphere.ecosystem.marine.solid earth (2022): FA,I,R

Figure 17: Network graph of shared FERs between all subdomains across all FAIR principles in 2022. The shared FERs are high-lighted as labels. Label size of the shared FERs reflects the number weighted with the implementation status and the distance between the RIs reflects their similarity in the FIP.

Figure 18: Density and implementation status of shared FERs grew stronger from 2019 to 2022. Each dot represents a reporting research infrastructure. Every line represents a bilaterally shared FER, the weaker a line, the lower the implementation status.

Based on the data provided, the average FER implementation status improved from 2.28 to 2.47 over the period covered by the analysis. This showed an improvement of the operational use of shared FERs across the RIs in ENVRI-FAIR (see Figure 18). The same trend is also shown by the analysis of the network cohesion, as inferred from the number and quality of shared FERs, which increased from 13 to 17 in the period analysed. The network cohesion shows that both number and implementation status of the shared FERs increased over time. This trend is also supported by the quantitative analysis of the number of shared FERs for the different subdomains (see Figure 15 and Table 12).

Figure 19 illustrates the progress of FERs from 2019 to 2022. The two positions of a given FER in each miniature portfolio reveal whether, over the project period, this FER became more common among the research infrastructures, or better implemented, or both.

A number of fair enabling resources (FERs) were prominently reported already in the 2019 survey: HTTPS and DOI, maybe not surprisingly, OPENDATA, CC-BY and PROV-O. These FERs not only held their position but increased their dominance by spread and/or mean implementation status until 2022. The largest mean implementation status improvement was reported for DataCite, while version BY-4.0 of the Creative Commons family experienced the fastest spread across RIs (Figure 19).

FER Progress 2019–2022

Figure 19: Average implementation status per shared FER, FAIR principle and year. Those FERs that dominated already in 2019 have become even more established in 2022.

3.1.4 Towards reference FAIR implementation profiles (rFIP)

The FAIR principles aim to promote the effective management, sharing, and reuse of digital assets, such as research data by the use and application of the different FERs. However, the principles alone can be somewhat abstract, and there can be variations their interpretation and implementation across different domains and contexts. By this a FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) is a list of declared technology choices (i.e., FERs) intended to implement each of the FAIR Guiding Principles, made as a collective decision by the members of a particular community of practice. It refers to a specific set of guidelines, standards, and best practices that are used to implement FAIR principles in a consistent and standardised manner.

In order to accelerate the convergence of RIs the development of a list of agreed FERs (Schultes et al. 2020) as well as “reference FIPs” as template for strategy and development planning. In this respect a “reference FIP” helps address this challenge by providing more specific and concrete guidance on how to put the FAIR principles into practice. The goal of a reference FAIR implementation profile is to provide a clear and practical framework for organisations and projects to follow when making their data or resources FAIR.

We tried to address this aspect by the comparison of the FIPs provided and identifying similarities. In addition, the qualitative analysis done in Chapter 3.1.3 is working in this direction. We used the FIPs from 2022 to perform a cluster analysis based on Manhattan-distance for the FIPs as well as for the FERs.

Figure 20: Over the years, the various FIPs became more homologous. By 2022, the FIPs of the research institutions had clustered into two major branches which in turn had gathered into more homologous subclusters.

Figure 20 shows the relative FIP-similarity across all repositories encountered. To recapitulate: FIP similarity is based on the repository-specific absence or presence of given items (=FERs) from the entire all-repository FER inventory (see Chapter 2.2). Remarkably, the clustering distinguished clearly between repositories the subdomain atmosphere and the remaining repositories (EISCAT being the only exception, Figure 20).

Reading the dendrogram from left to right, one can see that the repos split early into two major branches. One branch bundles all “atmospheric” repos (except EISCAT), the second branch contains the rest. This indicates that FIPs from the subdomain atmosphere share many characteristics, even though the “FER-fingerprint” of a given atmospheric repo will slightly differ from its siblings. It suggests that the convergence within the atmospheric subdomain is greatest. This could already be shown in the qualitative analysis of the subdomains. So based on the results at least for the atmospheric subdomain further work on defining a “reference FIP” would be possible. In contrast, the other repos do not separate into subdomain-specific branches but are well intermingled at any but the main branches’ level. Throughout this cluster, branches are quite long, meaning high dissimilarity between members’ FIPs. As a

consequence, the derivation of a reference FIP is (at this time) less promising than for the atmosphere repos (*viz.* infrastructures).

Likewise, the entire range of FERs separates into two distinct clusters when grouping by occurrence across the spectrum of repositories (Figure 21). However, these two groups rather reflect a divide between general purpose and RI-specific FERs than RI- or domain-specific differences, as suggested by the marked abundance differences between both clusters.

Figure 21: Top right: Graphical cluster overview graph: FAIR-enabling resources (FERs) formed two distinct clusters when grouped by their usage among repositories. Main: Number of Occurrences (y-axis) for the usage of the different FERs grouped in two clusters (red / blue). The two clusters showed pronounced differences in FER abundance, the red cluster being characterised by widespread (across repositories) FERs, the blue consisting of relatively rare FERs.

When comparing the results of the cluster analysis with the qualitative analysis shown in Table 12 on cluster level a similar pattern can be shown. Nevertheless, more work is needed to define and specify a “reference FIP” for the environmental domain.

3.2 ENVRI-FAIR Task Forces

In order to foster synergies and FAIRification of the environmental RIs a number of task forces have been organised to tackle the main technical challenges. They focused on all FAIR aspects aiming to integrate and support the environmental RIs in their implementation efforts.

One of the aims, especially by Task Force 6 was to support the design and development of the architecture and functionalities of the **ENVRI-HUB demonstrator**²¹ (Petzold et al., 2023; Deliverable D5.7 to be submitted June 2023), as a central access point not only to the use cases or scientific demonstrators but also the ENVRI Knowledge base, the ENVRI Service catalogue and the ENVRI Training platform (see Figure 22).

Figure 22: Structure of the ENVRI-Hub providing access to key exploitable results (© ENVRI-FAIR, <https://envri-hub.envri.eu/about>)

The ENVRI-Hub concept is designed as a federated system of harmonised subdomain/RI-specific systems of data policies and management, access platforms and virtual research environments (scientific demonstrators). The demonstrator is completely open source, modular and scalable and builds on the experience available in the consortium and already operational systems. In this respect both the environmental RIs as well as the task forces worked towards its implementation.

The task force “**PIDs identification types and registries**” (TF3)²² focusing mostly on the **Findability (F)** but with implications for all FAIR principles, aimed to raise awareness of the ENVRI-FAIR partners about the importance of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), associated concepts, and various technologies to implement them in day-to-day data management. PIDs are necessary requirements for FAIRness and are expressed in several of the FAIR principles. Also, the use of FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs) has been taken into account. The results were summarised in internal reports focusing on best practices for PIDs and the evolution of the PID usage in ENVRI-FAIR.

The task force on “**AAI implementation**” (TF2) focuses on specific aspects of **Accessibility (A)** dealing specifically with design and implementation of Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) within and between the different environmental RI. The overarching goal is to create a level of

²¹ see <https://envri-hub.envri.eu/>

²² see <https://fileshare.icos-cp.eu/s/f9tWMJFsWombCKx?path=%2F> for the Task Force report TF1-TF6

harmonisation across RIs so that they are interoperable and to establish a federation (on a voluntary basis) for authentication, enabling Single Sign-On (SSO) across RIs. The task force seeks to create policies to manage authorizations and to converge on key concepts, such as the AARC Blueprint architecture and the use of OIDC/OAuth2 as state-of-the-art technologies for AAI interoperability by a number of proof of concepts input for the further work.

Addressing the **Interoperability (I)** aspects the task force on “**Triple stores and data storage certification**” (TF4) was established focusing on semantic challenges to enhance the FAIRness of information provision as well as on trusted and certified repositories. Semantic harmonisation and integration is one of the important aspects to enhance convergence and interoperability between the different RIs. Special focus was laid on the results of the RDA work and especially I-ADOPT which was suggested to be adopted by the environmental RIs. Between January 2020 and December 2023, TF4 has made substantial contributions to technology adoption and convergence for triple store applications, data storage certification, ENVRI-Hub conceptualization, I-ADOPT Framework adoption, and ENVRI vocabulary for data quality. The number of ENVRIs using triple stores increased from 2 to 7 while the number of certifications increased from 1 to 3 during the 3-year period. During the same period, 3 ENVRIs have adopted the I-ADOPT Framework for the semantic description of measured variables. The task force “**Licences citation and usage tracking**” (TF5) focused on the **Re-usability (R)** which focused on the technical aspects of (meta)data licensing, data citation and data usage tracking (TF5 report, 2023)²³. The TF has identified the gaps of metadata schemas commonly used for research data in ENVRI RIs while focusing on the use cases occurring in these RIs. At the same time, the TF has developed a schema for data licence metadata that fills in these gaps.

The task force on (TF1) “**ENVRI Catalogue of Services**” worked towards an agreement on and implementation of a metadata catalogue schema and associated management services that will allow to describe and provide access to ENVRI assets. The aim was to prepare the ENVRI catalogue of services for the EOSC, ensuring that it is machine-readable and actionable. In order to achieve this goal, TF1 has been working on defining an overview paper (Bailo 2020) that propose the way forward, as well as converging on a common data model that is based on a refactored version of the CERIF²⁴ standard. The work done places the ENVRI community at the forefront of harmonisation and comparison work on FAIR/Open Science topics and demonstrates that ENVRIs are ready to take on these demanding and stimulating challenges.

4 Go far, go FAIR?

FIPs and FAIR Convergence

In the specific case of ENVRI-FAIR, numerous communities in the earth and environmental sciences have made FIPs as part of the self-assessment exercise. The resultant collection of FIPs, called the FIP Convergence Matrix, served as the starting point for systematic analysis and discussions to spot FIPs that were particularly reusable (repurposable). If even a subset (e.g., the RIs of a subdomain) of the ENVRI-FAIR communities could agree on, and implement towards, a single FIP (or a small collection of similar FIPs or a collection of core FERs), they could constitute the critical mass within the ENVRI-FAIR project precipitating commitments (formal or informal) by the other community members and indeed, the project as a whole. The impact of an ENVRI-FAIR “reference FIP” could extend beyond the project itself, becoming an attractor to relevant communities outside the project.

There are numerous attributes of a FIP that would make it a suitable attractor and trigger convergence. First, by inspecting each resource listed in the FIP, it is possible to calculate the degree to which the FIP maximises the reuse of already existing digital resources. Reuse of existing resources will save development time (i.e., avoiding the needless reinvention of the wheel) while also driving interoperation with those communities that use the resource already. However, more targeted analyses, based for example on extended questions for specific purposes, could explicitly measure the degree to which the FIP ensures semantic interoperation within a given domain or between domains. For example, interoperation could be optimised by carefully choosing terminologies used in describing observable properties and their related entities (e.g., the initiative to drive harmonisation by the RDA WG I-ADOPT

²³ information extracted from internal report of the task force 5 activities

²⁴ CERIF stands for Common European Research Information Format, a data model used to represent research information (“Main Features of CERIF,” euroCRIS, accessed February 20, 2023, <https://www.eurocris.org/cerif/main-features-cerif>).

[Magagna et al., 2022]). FERs can be evaluated against various maturity indicators [Wilkinson et al., 2022] and considering practical cost estimates for implementation.

Another important attribute of FERs is the frequency with which they are claimed and reused by other communities. The recognition and uptake can be fuelled by explicit endorsement by third-party stakeholders who may analyse trends among the global corpus of published FIPs and offer recommendations to maximise reuse and interoperability along various user dimensions. For example: trusted industry-wide organisations like the Pistoia Alliance, could be given the mandate to select or build FIPs for its pharmaceutical industry members; governments could do the same for the public sector; scientific societies could do this for scholarly research disciplines, including both the hard and soft sciences. Shareable FIPs can be used as a ‘default setting’ to kick-start the FIPs of other communities that aspire to adopt FAIR practices. However, organisations having cross-disciplinary or administrative mandates -- such as repositories and national archives, funding agencies or publishers -- may also define FIPs. In other cases, data-related organisations, the Research Data Alliance, CODATA, and the World Data System could also create and endorse FIPs.

Given the potential economic impact of “going FAIR” [8], there will likely emerge sophisticated FIP optimisation applications that could even introduce machine learning approaches. Advanced stages of FIP analysis will eventually lead to the identification and examination of FAIR technology ‘gaps’, triggering innovation in specialised FAIR technologies.

Given that suitable FIPs can be conceived, tested, published, and endorsed, there are at least two mechanisms by which FIPs can accelerate actual FAIR implementation in relatively short time frame:

1. *Trusted FIPs as defaults in the FIP Convergence Matrix*: The optimised FIPs composed, maintained and endorsed by trusted authorities can be offered in the Convergence Matrix as ‘one-click’ defaults for other communities to adopt and reuse, in whole or in part, as they see fit. For mature FIPs, this may come with guarantees on certain aspects of FAIR and levels of FAIRness. As trusted FIPs emerge, it becomes possible for communities wishing to enter the Matrix for the first time, to simply choose the FIP that has already proven its value in FAIR applications. Not only could widespread reuse of trusted FIPs lead to rapid uptake of FAIR among a broad spectrum of communities that otherwise might be ill-equipped to build their own, but it would also constitute a powerful mechanism of convergence on FAIR standards and technologies cross-cutting topical domains, private sector/public sector boundaries, and application spaces.
2. *Trusted FIPs as defaults in data stewardship plans*: Once a FIP becomes “official”, i.e., published in the FIP Convergence Matrix, it can be seen as the FAIR component of any data management/stewardship plan that may be subsequently filled by members of that community. For example, if the American Geophysical Union completed on behalf of its research community a FIP for geophysics data, then the AGU FIP could be accessed and reused (in whole or in part, with any appropriate modifications) by data stewards creating data stewardship plans in geophysics-related projects. By reusing FIPs, the many, often difficult, decisions required to ensure a high degree of FAIRness in geophysics can now be taken as defaults from the trusted authority of the AGU, saving significant time investment by data stewards across the research domain. Furthermore, the reuse of high-quality FIPs will pre-empt implementations chosen in local settings that lead to divergence or incompatibilities with other community FIPs. For example, reusable FIPs can serve to automatically pre-fill a DMP’s FIP-related answers. This application is currently under development in the GO FAIR Foundation.

Future directions

While the FIP procedure is meanwhile a widely adopted method (proven by its uptake by projects like WorldFAIR²⁵ and PARC²⁶) to landscape the use of FERs within communities there is still some room for optimization of the approach. Here we outline possible future improvements.

The FIP Wizard allows the user to either select a FER from the drop-down list of a specific question or to create a new resource using another targeted short questionnaire. It even allows to reuse existing

²⁵ <https://worldfair-project.eu/2023/06/22/worldfair-deliverable-webinar-series-fair-implementation-profiles-the-cross-domain-interoperability-framework-and-the-worldfair-methodology/>

²⁶ <https://www.eu-parc.eu/>

metadata published in FAIRsharing.org to create a nanopublication based machine readable FER. In case a user decides to provide a new FER description, no quality control mechanism makes sure that the resource itself can be considered FAIR enabling, or that the attributes provided are correct, for example, if the right resource types were chosen or not. As indicated in the FIP Wizard user guide (Schultes & Magagna 2023) a FIP creation should be guided via a trained 3 Point FAIRification Framework²⁷ facilitator whose major responsibility is to ensure the list of resources is uncluttered by duplicates or erroneous FERs. The facilitator has also the task to review a newly introduced FER description by checking its correctness and declares this by providing a nanopublication that states that the FER description is qualified. In the FIP Wizard these FERs are marked with the GFF qualification logo:

The capacity to qualify FERs is currently limited. In order to address a growing backlog, GFF now provides training to data stewards to become 3PFF facilitators. 12 PARC FAIR Implementation Task Force members will enforce the qualification team timely. GFF has also started a Fellows Programme²⁸ to transfer knowledge and skills in FAIR implementation.

As previously discussed, convergence of resources can be objectively measured by resource overlap but may also be achieved by the FAIRness of the resource. Thus, next to experience-based qualification by 3PFF facilitator the application of metrics of FAIRness should be used to actually measure the degree of compliance with the FAIR Principles via an automated FAIR assessment tool. The FAIR evaluator (Wilkinson et al., 2019) and F-UJI [Huber & Devaraju, 2021] are targeted to provide a measure for typical Digital Objects but necessarily for FAIR Enabling Resources. Specialised FAIR metrics should be developed for assessing the “FAIR readiness” of different FER types like vocabularies, registries or usage licences. GFF is in the process of developing a roadmap together with the F-UJI team to provide these automated evaluations of FAIR Readiness Levels for FERs. While resource overlap specifically related to the I Principles is preferable, convergence between semantic resources can also be achieved by mappings and crosswalks. However, this still remains a significant challenge.

The quality of a FER might also be described by its general uptake by communities. FAIR Connect is a platform under development aiming for the widespread adoption of FAIR implementation and is designed to capture the reuse of FERs.

The quality of FERs will thus be a combination of different qualification steps:

- a qualitative check by 3PFF facilitators
- an automatic check using metrics for FAIR Readiness Levels
- the extent of FER uptake number by communities

In addition, when compiled as a FIP, the list of FERs can be used as a basis for evaluation for FAIR Principle R1.3, as it explicitly represents the definitive collection of domain-relevant community standards.

To make FIPs more precise GFF is revising the FIP Ontology by including the research activity and the data type that is generated in the research activity of a specific community. This would be mirroring the tendency of some RIs to use their data repository as the filtering focus for their FIPs. The definition of reference FIPs by a cross-domain community like ENVRI-FAIR or its subdomain RIs interested to exchange interoperable data (as discussed in chapter 3.1.4) including only the minimal common FERs might be a promising route to go as it represents the minimal consensus upon FERs to be reused by any community.

5 Strategy and outlook

5.1 Goal and vision

ENVRI-FAIR is the connection of the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Participating research infrastructures (RI) of the environmental domain cover the subdomains Atmosphere, Marine, Solid Earth and, Biodiversity and Ecosystems and thus the Earth system in its full complexity. Global change research requires the integration of data from multiple disciplines to understand complex feedback mechanisms and their

²⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/2020/07/08/a-three-point-framework-for-fairification/>

²⁸ <https://osf.io/x43g7>

impact on the Earth system. FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) of digital (meta)data and services is therefore crucial for studying these interactions effectively.

ENVRI-FAIR aims to advance the integration and accessibility of environmental data and services by establishing a federated system fostering harmonized policies and management. Participating RIs build a set of FAIR data services which enhances the efficiency and productivity of researchers, supports innovation, enables data- and knowledge-based decisions, and connects the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC. In order to enable this, the ambition of ENVRI-FAIR is to establish the technical preconditions for the successful implementation of the ENVRI-Hub, a virtual, federated machine-to-machine interface linking FAIR RI (meta)data and services. Full integration of services across Research Infrastructures (RIs) and their subdomains is a continuous focus, with an emphasis on environmental data and scientific research objectives. Each RI specializes in specific parameters related to their competences. To accommodate users requiring broader or comprehensive environmental information, the ENVRI-Hub will provide a platform that reflects the complexity and diversity of the ENVRI landscape while preserving the individual structures and addressing the RI-specific requirements. The ENVRI-Hub will enable access to environmental data and services provided by the contributing ENVRIIs.

Implementing FAIR Principles is a long journey which will still take time. In this respect, FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP) are a good starting point for making the FAIR implementation choices (FERs) taken by a community transparent and identifying gaps. Once these FERs are identified for all involved communities it is possible to work towards convergence.

In order to foster cross-domain collaboration, the cross-cutting Task Forces involved representatives from all subdomains, bringing together technical, scientific, and managerial staff, and also fostered the sharing of knowledge and expertise. Common development targets were identified and common solutions to be translated into recommendations were provided. This work paves the way for defining the strategy for further future ENVRI development. Some future development areas are:

- Ingestion of further metadata records from the Subdomains into the Catalogue of Services. This includes support to communities with appointed metadata editors for updating and integrating metadata records.
- Improvement of the quality of the metadata records (a) to provide a better user experience; (b) to align with the EOSC catalogue requirements.
- More semantic work on making vocabularies consistent and more interoperable, and to provide a set of keywords that enable a simple discovery of the available services.
- EOSC Onboarding of the Catalogue of Services.
- Implementation of custom community AAI solutions at different levels of maturity and varying degrees of compliance with the EOSC AAI interoperability guidelines.
- Federated (semantic) search based on metadata standards.
- Development of a data analytical framework.

Based on the analysis of the development of the ENVRIIs covering the domains (a) atmosphere, (b) marine, (c) solid earth, and (d) biodiversity and ecosystem major efforts have been taken to enhance the FAIRness of the (meta)data and services. A number of shared FERs could be identified, but still efforts need to be taken to establish clear reference FIPs for further development. Dobler et al. (2023) have formulated 10 recommendations for a sustainable data management in the marine domain, which provide an important input for the future strategy of the RI development and the integration of services into the EOSC.

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 Overall FAIRness

The FAIRification of not only data but also services enables the convergence of data streams across research infrastructures providing a benefit for the wider scientific community but also increases cost-efficiency which leads to a more effective spending of funding. The FAIRness of data, metadata, and services must therefore be continuously improved for sustained data management. This involves ensuring proper description, traceability, findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Examples of enhancements include accessible change history, cloud solutions for improved dataset accessibility,

extended ontologies to meet user needs, and enhanced visualisation in services. User feedback is crucial to maintaining system relevance for both human and machine users. Curation actions, selection of FAIR-enhancing solutions, and flexible architecture are guided by user requirements. The ENVRI-FAIR project developed quantitative indicators that showed improved FAIR coverage and convergence toward common technologies. To progress, the assessment of FAIRness should also consider quality aspects, such as machine-to-machine health procedures, non-regression procedures during service upgrades, and human check procedures for data accessibility.

This means that the FAIR Assessment should be implemented as a continuous process and service for RIs in order to check quantity as well as quality of the FERs used.

- **Recommendation** (Dobler et al. 2023, recommendation 3) - The FAIRness assessment should be improved to include the assessment of the quality of the implementation for the FERs.

5.2.2 Findability (F)

A number of different **persistent identification systems (PIDs, F1)** are used by the different RIs which are mainly implemented on the level of metadata of datasets. Nevertheless, the use of global unique and persistent identifiers (GU-PID) is an important prerequisite for enhancing the findability of the data. The persistence of the identifier is the most important aspect and depends on the policy applied by the provider. The TF on “PIDs, identification types and registries” provided a white paper on relevant PIDs systems²⁹ and a document mapping the evolution of the use of PIDs in the ENVRI context³⁰. As shown in the analysis on the cluster level DOIs and Handle System (e.g., B2HANDLE, ePIC handle) are the most commonly used PIDs for (meta)data. On metadata level many RIs implement UUIDs (Universally Unique Identifiers) for the identification. In contrast to DOIs and Handle Systems, the persistence relies on the policy and sustainability of the local RI infrastructure. In addition, a number of PIDs for non-data entities are used by some RIs (e.g., ORCID, ROR, deims.id, sios-site) but there is no common adoption across the RIs.

- **Recommendations** by TF on “PIDs, identification types and registries”
 - Interoperability and machine-actionability of ENVRI datasets and data services need further enhancement, including assigning PIDs to non-data resources and using PIDs in catalogue metadata records.
 - Engagement with external groups like the EOSC Association, Research Data Alliance, and FAIR Digital Object Forum is crucial for addressing ENVRI's needs in persistent identifier-related applications and services.

To enhance the findability and interoperability among RI assets a common and harmonised subset of **metadata (sub-principle F2)** elements is needed to enable the search across the different RI catalogues. In addition, the provision of quality-assured, rich, and machine-readable metadata is an important prerequisite for the integration, discovery, and use of data. The use of common metadata schemas is important and should be a focus in the FAIR convergence. For this crosswalks between the MD schemas are important and should be provided/developed. The analysis showed a broad range of different metadata schemas applied by the different RIs, which is often due to the community requirements. ISO19115/19139 for geo-spatial data is one of the common metadata schemas used across the different subdomains. Nevertheless, when addressing mappings between different schemas semantic heterogeneity, structural differences, mapping complexities, maintenance, and evolution of the schemas, as well as their governance and consistency have to be taken into account (Basset et al. 2023). Nevertheless, within TF1 on “ENVRI Catalogue of services” was done towards the agreement in a white paper, on adopting CERIF as the underlying schema, and ingesting metadata records via EPOS-DCAT-AP.

- **Recommendation** (Dobler et al. 2023, adapted, recommendation 4) - To enhance the metadata integration, each RI should extend of enhance the subset of common metadata descriptions,

²⁹ see https://docs.google.com/document/d/1KXeh5BMgR4RGXcFf8TTEUPFJrCg9OhFpLky_Fy4qA7c/edit# (internal document)

³⁰ see <https://docs.google.com/document/d/19-yNuoajHBIPvDrwBSLoT9KWFKBguYtamRYxRS9Li3U/edit#> (internal document)

following a common recommendation, and if relevant (e.g., for quality codes, keywords) map existing vocabularies to a common vocabulary.

- **Recommendation** (Basset et al. 2023, adapted) - Collaborative efforts, the use of standardized interoperability frameworks and protocols, development of common vocabularies and ontologies, and continuous coordination among infrastructure providers. It also calls for the adoption of data integration approaches and technologies that enable harmonization and alignment of metadata across different schemas.

Providing **common discovery interfaces (subprinciple F4)** for end-users as well as for aggregators should enhance the discoverability and accessibility of (meta)data. An important aspect is the quality of the registries in terms of information covered and ingested from the providing MD sources. The use of shared indexing registries (e.g., GEOSS) is important and a common use of them within a given domain is important. The analysis of the FERs on cluster level showed a broad range of RI specific (e.g., ICOS Carbon Portal), community specific as well as cross-domain and global metadata aggregators (e.g., GEOSS, Google Data Search). In this respect Basset et al. (2023) state that *“While it may seem advantageous to have a unified data portal or metadata catalogue, the diverse needs, complexities, governance considerations, and community-building aspects make it more practical and effective for RIs to develop their own data portals and metadata catalogues. These dedicated platforms ensure tailored support for domain-specific research, enable specialized data management functionalities, maintain control over governance and policies, and foster collaboration within their respective communities.”*

- **Recommendation** - The development of the ENVRI-Hub as common interface between RI data and services and the EOSC service catalogue should be fostered and further developed in the frame of the ENVRIs. By this single RIs can contribute to regional, domain specific or global aggregators as well as to the ENVRI-Hub as a single point of access for users as well as to exchange service and data descriptions in a machine-2-machine manner.

5.2.3 Accessibility (A)

The use of common and open protocols for the **exchange of metadata and data to enable cross system implementation (subprinciple A1.1)** is an important feature to ensure the machine-2-machine interaction.

- Recommendation - HTTP should be avoided and replaced by HTTPS for security reasons

The use of interoperable **authorisation and authentication systems (sub-principle A1.2)** is important to establish cross-RI services. An overlap of authentication and authorisation procedures is therefore beneficial. The analysis showed a broad range of different AA procedures implemented at the RI level. Many of the RIs apply an Open Data Policy which does not require authorisation and authentication for data access. Nevertheless, in order to upload data or make use of services authentication and authorisation is needed. TF 2 on “Authorisation and Authentication” worked towards a whitepaper and architecture to enhance the accessibility of (meta)data and services across subdomains. Still efforts need to be taken in this respect beyond the runtime of the ENVRI-FAIR project.

- Recommendation (based on TF2 conclusions) - Convergence on key concepts, including the adoption of the AARC Blueprint architecture and convergence on OIDC/OAuth2 as state-of-the-art technologies for AAI interoperability.

5.2.4 Interoperability (I)

As apparent even over a four years’ period, FERs are technologically volatile: sharing licences evolve, vocabularies branch and merge, network protocols become superseded etc. This implies that convergence must remain flexible enough to adopt innovation - a challenge not to be underestimated, considering the necessary conceptual and technological consensus among RIs (and eventually budgets) required. Particularly the principle of interoperability involves a trade-off between rigid formal and technological bundling (to enhance exchange) and diversification (to support flexibility and agility) of the operational backbone.

- **Recommendation** - Embrace emerging FAIR-supporting technology, but favour generalizability, scalability and open source over specificity, novelty or proprietary tools - particularly when replacing existing resources. When extending existing formats (e. g. XML templates), make sure the vital information stays in the core scheme (again, favour interoperability over fine-grained specificity).

This principle focuses on the use of **formal, shared and broadly applicable languages for knowledge representation (sub-principle I1)**. A common shared use of data formats and schemas is beneficial and mappings are needed to ensure interoperability. The analysis showed that XML (eXtensible Markup Language), mostly used for metadata, and NetCDF (Network Common Data Format), used for scientific data that provides a self-describing and machine-independent way to store multidimensional data, are the most commonly used schemas. Nevertheless, a broad range of community specific formats and languages are used raising the needs for mapping and transformation services. The RDA WG on Data Type Model and Registry is working on recommendations to enhance interoperability and transferability of data and metadata.

- **Recommendation** - Common use of a Data Type Registry for data and metadata schemas should be applied

The use of common and **shared vocabularies (subprinciple I2)** following FAIR principles should be fostered and is beneficial. In addition, mappings between vocabularies are needed to ensure interoperability.

- **Recommendation** (Dobler et al. 2023, adapted, recommendation 4) - To enhance the metadata integration, each RI should extend of enhance the subset of common metadata descriptions, following a common recommendation, and if relevant (e.g., for quality codes, keywords) map existing vocabularies to a common vocabulary.
- **Recommendation** (based on TF4 conclusions)
 - the use of triple stores for vocabulary management and access as well as
 - provenance metadata management has received broad interest and is surely also of interest beyond ENVRI-FAIR. that a platform for (technology) knowledge exchange can support efficient and effective technology adoption and convergence, which simplifies the overall ecosystem and likely increases its interoperability with lower needs for translation and mapping.
 - adoption of the I-ADOPT recommendations for the description of measured variables to enhance mappability and interoperability.

5.2.5 Re-usability (R)

This principle focuses on providing a **clear and accessible data usage licence (subprinciple R1.1)** enabling the re-usability. Machine-readability is beneficial to ensure re-usability.

- **Recommendation** (based on TF5 conclusions) - Commonly accepted and machine-readable data licenses (e.g., CC-licenses) should be used and data license metadata schema should be published, e.g., on schema.org

R1.2 The description of provenance in the data life cycle is an important part of the re-usability and acknowledgement. Overlap of models to describe provenance is beneficial. Otherwise, mappings between provenance models are needed. Still provenance in a machine-readable manner is not established by all RIs.

- **Recommendation** (based on TF5 conclusions) - the documentation of the provenance should be fostered using common applied models, as e.g., PROV-O

5.2.6 General aspects

Certification and accreditation of data centres

- **Recommendation** (based on TF4 report) - It is an important milestone for any RI as it acts as a “trust label” for stakeholders depositing or consuming data. With certification schemes by World Data Systems (WDS), Data Seal of Approval (DSA), CoreTrustSeal (CTS), nestor seal, ISO, etc. data storage certification is, however, an increasingly complex area to navigate. While these schemes can be sorted along a “prestige gradient” they also entail varying degrees of complexity and requirements.
- **Recommendation** (based on TF4 report) - Certification and accreditation of data centres of the RIs should be fostered in the future.

Software development

The RI and research community faces a growing demand for code sharing, which is crucial for ensuring transparency and reproducibility within and beyond the community. To facilitate effective code sharing, it is recommended that data management software transitions towards open-source and open science frameworks, as well as cloud-native implementations whenever suitable. This strategic shift will foster enhanced collaboration in software development, promote knowledge sharing, and foster a broader community of developers and data managers, both within and beyond the RIs. These initiatives collectively contribute to the long-term sustainability of the technological tools employed by the RIs.

- Recommendation (Dobler et al. 2023, recommendation 6) - To facilitate code sharing, data management software should move towards open source and open science frameworks and/or cloud-native implementations, when possible and relevant.

Integration into EOSC

Thijsse et al. (2023) summarised the results of the testing and validation of ENVRI-FAIR services and EOSC, with the aim to feedback to the RIs and to enhance the integration and sharing of services through the EOSC catalogue. The ENVRI-Hub in this respect can be an important aggregator and interface towards the EOSC platform.

- **Recommendation** (Thijsse et al. 2023, adapted) - The EOSC marketplace offers increased visibility to the individual ENVRI services in parallel to them also becoming visible via the ENVRI catalogue of services as a whole on the marketplace. Services from the subdomains should onboard their services to the EOSC marketplace, to increase visibility and make use of the EOSC core or horizontal services they see fit.
- **Recommendation** - The development of the ENVRI-Hub as common interface between RI data and services and the EOSC service catalogue should be fostered and further developed in the frame of the ENVRI. By this single RIs can contribute to regional, domain specific or global aggregators as well as to the ENVRI-Hub as a single point of access for users as well as to exchange service and data descriptions in a machine-2-machine manner.

5.3 Gateway to ENVRI - the ENVRI-Hub

ENVRI-FAIR aims to connect the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (Petzold et al. 2023). The ENVRI-FAIR project seeks to establish the necessary technical foundations for a virtual, federated machine-to-machine interface expressed by the **ENVRI-Hub concept, which can enable access to environmental data and services provided by contributing ENVRI**. The ENVRI-Hub concept corresponds to a federated system comprising harmonized subdomain/RI-specific data policies, management systems, access platforms, and virtual research environments. This open-source, modular, and scalable system will leverage semantic web technology and ontologies to facilitate integration of metadata and data objects across RIs and subdomains. By promoting interoperability and following a modular design, the ENVRI-Hub will foster efficiency, robustness, and the development of higher-level services. It will ensure seamless integration with EOSC services, such as AAI, data storage solutions, and service catalogues. As a result of the ENVRI-FAIR project a prototype has been developed based on this concept, to demonstrate the improved FAIRness of the ENVRI. The ENVRI-Hub demonstrator functionalities and content include

data and service discovery, cross-domain search, access to thematic services, the ENVRI Training Platform and Science Demonstrators.

The ENVRI-Hub can serve as a common portal and complementary access path to RI digital assets, becoming part of the EOSC and other systems. The design and architecture of the ENVRI-Hub is driven by user requirements, science demonstrators, and the need for interoperability at all levels (Deliverable D5.7, to be submitted June 2023). Science demonstrators, aligned with cross-subdomain science questions, will inform the ENVRI-Hub's development, in coordination with the EOSC Future project. Ultimately, ENVRI-FAIR and ENVRI-Hub will facilitate open data sharing, support scientific research, and contribute to the goals of the EOSC.

Policies for the ENVRI-Hub

The ENVRI-Hub facilitates user and API access to the digital asset catalogue provided by ENVRI Research Infrastructures (RIs). Access to the ENVRI catalogue is regulated by policies implemented through guidelines and IT solutions. RIs have the autonomy to determine the manner and conditions under which they expose their digital assets to the ENVRI-Hub and the wider EOSC community. This is achieved by exporting or harvesting metadata from their RI catalogue into the ENVRI-Hub catalogue. The ENVRI-Hub must establish its own policies, guidelines, and IT infrastructure, which may differ from those of individual RIs. It is desirable to document access conditions within metadata, aligning with the principles of ENVRI-FAIR. Additionally, comprehensive policies addressing privacy, terms and conditions, and cookies should be in place, along with appropriate acknowledgement and consent procedures.

Based on the findings Asmi et al. (2023) identified key policy areas for the ENVRI-Hub future implementation which needs to be addressed:

- Curation: Availability of digital assets) and FAIR
- Security (protection of digital assets)
- Privacy (personal data)
- Authorisation of access (protection of digital assets and recording for provenance, citation and usage requires authentication)
- Licensing (protection of digital assets: name of licence and authorisation parameters)
- Provenance: (tracking of asset evolution and use for privacy)
- Citation (tracking for accreditation of researcher)
- Usage tracking (for statistics indicating popularity and usage of personal data)

These policies, guidelines and development needs to be applied both on the level of the single RIs and asset suppliers as well as on the level of the ENVRI-Hub. This is also important to achieve conformant policies for interoperation among RIs and ENVRI-Hub and onward to EOSC. Further work on this, needs to be a strategic area for the future developments.

6 Summary

ENVRI-FAIR is a project that aims to connect the ESFRI Cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures (ENVRI) to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) with the goal is to integrate a set of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) (meta)data and services that enhance the efficiency and productivity of researchers, support innovation, enable data-driven decisions, and connect the ENVRI Cluster to the EOSC. To achieve this, ENVRI-FAIR aims to foster FAIR RI services linked in a machine-to-machine manner via the ENVRI-Hub. The project emphasizes the integration of services across different research infrastructures with a specific focus on environmental data and scientific research objectives. The ENVRI-Hub will provide a platform that reflects the complexity and diversity of the ENVRI landscape while accommodating users' broader or comprehensive environmental information needs.

The FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) of (meta)data and services is crucial for effective global change research and understanding the complex interactions within the Earth system. The implementation of FAIR principles is an ongoing process, and ENVRI-FAIR aims to make the FAIR implementation choices transparent and identify gaps through FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIP). This allows for convergence among the involved communities. Cross-domain collaboration is fostered through the involvement of representatives from all subdomains in cross-cutting Task Forces, promoting

knowledge sharing and expertise exchange. Within the work done we tried to identify common development targets, provide recommendations, and contribute to defining the strategy for future ENVRI development.

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9 Annex

1.1. Annex A: Abbreviations

3PFF	3 Point FAIRification Framework
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research Collaborations
API	Application Programming Interface
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
ATM	ENVRI-FAIR subdomain ‘atmosphere’
B2FIND	EUDAT data discovery catalogue service
B2HANDLE	EUDAT minting, storing, managing and accessing persistent identifiers
CDI	Common Data Index (metadata format and data access system by SeaDataNet)
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
CTS	Core Trust Seal
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DCAT	Data Catalogue Vocabulary
DMP	1) Data Management Plan 2) Data Management Platform (WP9)
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DSA	Data Seal of Approval
DSW	Data Stewardship Wizard
ECO	ENVRI-FAIR subdomain ‘ecosystem and biodiversity’
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures (in ESFRI level or upcoming) as a community
ENVRIplus	An environmental RI cluster H2020 project
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium (legal entity type)
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EUDAT	European Data Infrastructure
FA	FAIR assessment
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
FER	FAIR Enabling Resource
FIC	FAIR Implementation Community
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
FMI	FAIR Maturity Indicator
FORC	Future of Research Communication
FORCE11	The Future of Research Communication and e-Scholarship (gre out from FORC Workshop in 2011)
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFF	GO-FAIR Foundation

GO FAIR	An international programme on FAIR implementation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GUPRI	Global Unique Persistent and Referable Identifier
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
ICOS	Integrated Carbon Observation System
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IRI	Internationalised Resource Identifier
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LW	LifeWatch
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
MAR	ENVRI-FAIR subdomain 'marine'
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OAUTH	Open Authorization (standard)
OBIS	Ocean Biogeographic Information System
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifiers
PROV-O	Web Ontology Language encoding of the PROV Data Model
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF	Resource Description Framework
rdflib	RDF Python library
RDM	Research Database Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
SEADATANET	SeaDataNet pan-European infrastructure for marine data management
SHARC IG	SHARing Rewards and Credit Interest Group
SMTP	Simple Mail Transfer Protocol
SOL	ENVRI-FAIR subdomain 'solid earth'
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
TF	ENVRI-FAIR Task Forces
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WDS	World Data System of International Science Council
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
YaT	YAML Template

9.1 Annex B - List of unique FERs

FER: Fair Enabling Resource, Pr.: supported FAIR principle(s)

no.	Fair Enabling Resource (FER)	Pr.	last reported
1	ABCD Access to Biological Collection Data	I	2022
2	ABCDEFGH Access to Biological Collection Databases Extended for Geosciences	I	2022
3	ACTRIS Data Centre node for cloud profiling (CLU)	F	2022
4	ACTRIS Data Portal	F	2022
5	ACTRIS Vocabulary	I	2022
6	AERIS vocabulary	I	2021
7	ALIENSPECIES Alien Species Thesaurus	I	2022
8	AnaEE Metadata Preservation Policy	A	2022
9	anaeeThes AnaEE Thesaurus	I	2022
10	Aquatic Sciences and Fisheries Thesaurus	I	2022
11	Argo floats ERDDAP server	F	2022
12	Argo GDAC Argo floats metadata dashboard	F	2022
13	Argo GDAC long term archive	A	2022
14	Argo Opensearch API	F	2022

no.	Fair Enabling Resource (FER)	Pr.	last reported
15	B2FIND	F	2022
16	B2HANDLE	F	2022
17	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International	R	2022
18	CC BY-NC 4.0 Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International	R	2022
19	CC BY-ND 4.0 Attribution-NoDerivatives 4.0 International	R	2022
20	CC BY 4.0 Attribution 4.0 International	R	2022
21	CC BY SA 4.0 Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International	R	2022
22	CC0 1.0 CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication	R	2022
23	CERIF Common European Research Information Format	I,R	2022
24	CF SN Climate and Forecast Standard Names Parameter Vocabulary	I	2022
25	CKAN Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network	I,F	2022
26	CLU ACTRIS Data Centre node for cloud profiling	F	2022
27	CSW Catalog Service for the Web	A	2022
28	DAAI DiSSCo Federated Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure	A	2022
29	Danubius Demonstrator Portal	F	2022
30	DANUBIUS Preservation Policy	A	2022
31	DARA DOI registration agency for social and economic data	F	2021
32	Data Management plan for ACTRIS	A	2022
33	DataCite DataCite Ontology	F	2022
34	DataCite Metadata Scheme	F,I,R	2022
35	DC Dublin Core	I	2022
36	DCAT-AP Data Catalog Vocabulary Application Profile for Data Portals in Europe	I,F,R	2022
37	DCAT Data Catalog Vocabulary Version 2	I,F	2022
38	DCAT Data Catalog Vocabulary Version 3	F,I	2022
39	DEIMS-SDR-REST-API	A	2022
40	DEIMS-SDR Dynamic Ecological Information Management System - Site and Dataset Registry	F	2022
41	DEIMS-SDR_Site_Metadata_Model	I	2022
42	DEIMS.ID	F	2022
43	DIF Directory Interchange Format	F,I	2022
44	Dimensions	F	2022
45	DIRAC File Catalogue	A	2021
46	DiSSCo Data Management Plan	A	2022
47	DOI Digital Object Identifier	F	2022
48	DOIP Digital Object Interface Protocol	A	2022
49	DwC-A Darwin Core Archive	I,R	2022
50	EBAS database	F	2022
51	ECOI DiSSCo European Collection Objects Index	F	2022
52	EcoPortal	F	2022
53	eduGAIN Interfederation Service	A	2022
54	EGI Checkin	A	2022
55	EISCAT Data Licence	R	2021
56	EISCAT Data Policy and Licence	R,A	2022
57	EISCAT IP Address Check	A	2020
58	EISCAT Level 3 HDF5 archival format	I	2022
59	EISCAT Schedule	F	2022
60	eLTER-CDN eLTER Central Data Node	F	2022
61	eLTER Controlled Lists	I	2022
62	eLTER Data Management Plan Draft	A	2022
63	eLTER Digital Asset Registry	F	2022
64	eLTER DIP eLTER Data Integration	F	2022
65	eLTER_Data_Specification_Draft	I	2022
66	EML Ecological Metadata Language	F,I	2022
67	EML GBIF Profile Metadata Ecological Metadata Language Global Biodiversity Information Facility Profile Metadata	F,I,R	2022
68	EML2.2.0 Ecological Metadata Language 2.2.0	F,I	2022

no.	Fair Enabling Resource (FER)	Pr.	last reported
69	EnvThes Environmental Thesaurus	I	2022
70	ePIC Persistent Identifier Consortium for eResearch	F	2022
71	EPOS-DCAT-AP	F	2022
72	EPOS Common Vocabulary	I	2022
73	EPOS Data Policy	A	2022
74	EPOS ICS Data Portal	F	2022
75	EPOS Metadata Model	F	2022
76	ERDDAP	A,I,F	2022
77	EUNIS Habitat Classification	I	2022
78	Euro-ARGO Data Selection	F	2022
79	EUROCHAMP Data Format	I	2022
80	European Plate Observing System - Data Catalogue vocabulary - Application Profile	F,I	2022
81	FAIR Signposting	F	2022
82	FDO Fair Digital Object	F	2022
83	FISHTRAITS Fish Traits Thesaurus	I	2022
84	FTP File Transfer Protocol	A	2022
85	GAWSIS Global Atmosphere Watch Station Information System	F	2022
86	GBIF search engine Global Biodiversity Information Facility Search Engine	F	2022
87	GCMD Keywords Global Change Master Directory Keywords	I	2022
88	GEMET General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus	I	2022
89	Generic Earth Observation Metadata Standard	I	2022
90	GeoDCAT-AP	F,I	2022
91	GEOMS Generic Earth Observation Metadata Standard	I	2022
92	GeoNetwork	F	2022
93	GeoNetwork account in the internal catalog database	A	2022
94	GEOSS Portal Global Earth Observation System of Systems Portal	F	2022
95	GNU General Public License v3.0 or later	R	2021
96	Google Dataset Search	F	2022
97	Google Search	F	2022
98	GPL-2.0-or-later GNU General Public License v2.0 or later	R	2021
99	Handle System	F	2022
100	HDF5 archival file format for data in Madrigal	I	2022
101	HTTP Hypertext Transfer Protocol	A	2022
102	HTTPS Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure	A	2022
103	I-ADOPT Framework	I	2022
104	IAGOS Data Policy	R	2022
105	IAGOS Data Preservation Policy	A	2022
106	ICOS Carbon Portal Integrated Carbon Observation System Data Portal	F	2022
107	ICOS local account	A	2022
108	ICOS Ontology Integrated Carbon Observation System Ontology	I	2022
109	IMIS MetaData Preservation Policy	A	2022
110	In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System Data Portal	F	2022
111	InnovAuth	A	2022
112	INSPIRE EMF Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community Environmental Monitoring Facilities	I,F	2022
113	INSPIRE registry	I	2020
114	ISO 19115 Geographic information - Metadata	F,I,R	2022
115	ISO 19139 Geographic information - Metadata - XML schema implementation	F,I,R	2022
116	ISO 3166-1:2013 Codes for the representation of names of countries and their subdivisions - Part 1: Country codes	I	2022
117	IUCN International Union for Conservation of Nature - Red List of Threatened Species	I	2022
118	IUPAC Gold Book	I	2022
119	Joint Committee on Atomic and Molecular Physical data - working group on Data eXchange	I	2022
120	JPEG File Format	I	2022

no.	Fair Enabling Resource (FER)	Pr.	last reported
121	JSON-LD JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data	I	2022
122	JSON JavaScript Object Notation	I	2022
123	JSON Schema JavaScript Object Notation Schema	I	2022
124	Keycloak Single-Sign On	A	2022
125	LDAP Lightweight Directory Access Protocol	A	2022
126	LifeWatch ERIC Metadata Catalogue	I,F	2022
127	Linked Data Event Streams	A	2022
128	LOD Linked Open Data	F	2022
129	LUPO LifeWatch ERIC Upper Ontology	I	2022
130	LW_CO LifeWatch core ontology	I	2021
131	MACROALGAETRAITS Macroalgae Traits Thesaurus	I	2022
132	MADRIGAL data model	I	2022
133	MADRIGAL database	F	2022
134	Marine Regions georeferences	I	2022
135	MET Norway Metadata Format Specification	F	2022
136	MMD Vocabulary	I	2022
137	NASA Ames Format The National Aeronautics and Space Administration Ames Format for Data Exchange	I	2022
138	NetCDF Network Common Data Form	I	2022
139	NetCDF CF-1.7	F,I,R	2022
140	NetCDF_CF_SDN NETCDF CF format SeaDataNet Profile	I	2022
141	NSId Natural Science Identifier	F	2021
142	NVS NERC Vocabulary Service	I	2022
143	OAI-PMH Schema Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema	A	2022
144	OAuth Open Authorization	A	2022
145	OBOE-AnaEE ontology	I	2022
146	OBOE Extensible Observation Ontology	I	2022
147	OceanSITES OceanSITES Data Format	F,I	2022
148	ODV_ASCII Ocean Data View ASCII format for marine datasets	I	2022
149	OGC-SensorThings	I	2022
150	OGC CS Open Geospatial Consortium Catalogue Services 3.0	A	2022
151	OGC SensorML Open Geospatial Consortium Sensor Model Language	I,F,R	2022
152	Open Data	A	2022
153	OpenAIRE Research Graph	F	2022
154	OPeNDAP Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol	A	2022
155	openDS Open Digital Specimen	F,I	2022
156	OpenID Connect	A	2022
157	OpenSearch	A,F	2022
158	ORCID Open Researcher and Contributor ID	A,F	2022
159	OWL Web Ontology Language	I	2022
160	PANGAEA Data Publisher	F	2020
161	Parthenos Entities	I	2021
162	PHYTOTRAITS The Phytoplankton Traits	I	2022
163	PITHIA-NRF e-Science Centre search engine	F	2022
164	Portable Document Format (PDF)	I	2022
165	Portable Network Graphics (PNG)	I	2022
166	PROV-O W3C PROV Ontology	R	2022
167	PURL Persistent Uniform Resource Locator	F	2022
168	Python programming library ICOSCP	A	2022
169	RDA CTS RDA Core Trust Seal Certification	A	2020
170	RDF Resource Description Framework	I	2022
171	RDFS Resource Description Framework Schema	I	2022
172	re3data Registry of Research Data Repositories	F	2022
173	REST Representational state transfer	A	2022
174	ROR Research Organization Registry	F	2022
175	SAML1.1 Security Assertion Markup Language 1.1	A	2022
176	SAML2 Security Assertion Markup Language 2.0	A	2022

no.	Fair Enabling Resource (FER)	Pr.	last reported
177	Schema.org Dataset	F,I	2022
178	SDM MD SeaDataNet metadata directories	I	2022
179	SDN-CDI-Search SeaDataNet CDI search user interface	F	2022
180	SDN-MID-Service SeaDataNet Marine ID AAA service	A	2022
181	SDN-Sextant SeaDataNet Sextant search engines	F	2022
182	SDN CDI PID SeaDataNet CDI PID	F	2022
183	SDN CDI PID LUI SeaDataNet CDI to PID lookup index	F	2022
184	SDN DA L 1.0 SeaDataNet Data Access License 1.0	R	2020
185	SDN DP SeadataNet Data Policy and User License	R	2020
186	SDN2_CDI_ISO19139 SeaDataNet CDI metadata XML schema	F,I	2022
187	SEANOE - SEA scieNtific Open data Edition	F	2020
188	SIOS Data Management Plan	A	2022
189	Sios Metadata Search	F	2022
190	SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System	I	2022
191	SOS Sensor Observation Service	A	2022
192	Space Physics Ontology	I	2022
193	SPARQL (open) endpoint	A,F	2022
194	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System CSW Catalogue	F	2022
195	Tag Image File Format (TIFF)	I	2022
196	The ICOS Preservation Policy	A	2022
197	URI Uniform Resource Identifier	F	2022
198	UUID Universally Unique Identifier	F	2022
199	WCS Web Coverage Service	A	2022
200	WFS Web Feature Service	A	2022
201	WIGOS WMO Integrated Global Observing System	F,I	2022
202	WMO Core Profile World Meteorological Organization Core Metadata Profile	F,I	2022
203	WMO Search World Meteorological Organization Search	F	2022
204	WMS Web Map Service	A	2022
205	WoRMS World Register of Marine Species	I	2022
206	XMLS eXtensible Markup Language Schema	I	2022